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**PERCEIVED CONFLICT AND PROFESSIONALISM AMONG NURSES IN A
TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA**

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PERCEIVED CONFLICT AND PROFESSIONALISM AMONG NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: **“PERCEIVED CONFLICT AND PROFESSIONALISM AMONG NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SAUDI ARABIA”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Arts in Nursing.

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Biographical Sketch

Abigail Ruth G. Padua is a Registered Nurse. She graduated from Saint Louis University, Baguio City, in 2003 with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree. She began her career as a bedside nurse at Pines City Doctor's Hospital for a duration of three years before transitioning to work in Saudi Arabia. She returned to the Philippines and pursued a career in academia. After spending two years as a clinical instructor, she decided to return to her passion for bedside care. She joined the Nursery staff at a prestigious tertiary hospital in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in 2009 and later assumed the role of a Unit Manager. In her current position, she is responsible for overseeing Quality Initiatives, Accreditation, and Risk Management in Women's Specialized hospital. She is a career-driven individual with a strong interest in quality care, nursing operations, leadership, and management.

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Above all, I express my utmost gratitude and devotion to God, who is the source of my existence and the wisdom I possess.

Dedication

I want to dedicate my thesis to my loving parents **Humbert and Perly**. My devoted partner, **Sonny** and to my three precious gems, **Gunther Craig, Maryam Layl and Adam Omar**, whose presence in my life has brought immeasurable joy. They have served as my source of inspiration in order to successfully complete this academic journey.

Abstract

The worldwide health care sector is changing rapidly, causing conflicts at work and this has led to extensive discussions on professionalism in healthcare settings. The study on the correlation between conflict and professionalism is currently lacking in terms of the necessary contextual information and relevant literature that could potentially fill this gap. The primary purpose of this study was to identify and examine the correlation between perceived levels of conflict, including interpersonal conflict, intrapersonal conflict, intergroup conflict, and intragroup conflict, and perceived level of professionalism, encompassing outlook on nursing as a profession, job position of the nurses, and the relationship of the nurse to the client/patient as well as the physician and other health team colleagues. It also examines the influence of socio-demographic profile on nurses' level of conflict and professionalism. The researcher was motivated to contribute to addressing this issue. This Descriptive correlational study describes the variables and the relationships that occur between and among them. A total of 483 nurses working in the tertiary hospital were recruited using simple random technique. The Perceived Conflict Scale (PCS) and The Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (VCNS) was used for data collection. The mean and standard deviation were utilized to describe the perceptions of participants and the variability of their responses regarding the perceived level of conflict and professionalism among nurses. Pearson Correlation analyzed the relationship between conflict and professionalism and chi square between nurses' conflict and professionalism and the sociodemographic profile of respondents. Generally, Nurses in the tertiary hospital have a high level of conflict except level of Intragroup Conflict which is low. Moreover, Staff nurses have a high level of professionalism and nurses' perceptions of conflict

and years of experience were not statistically significantly associated with one another. Furthermore, there was no significant correlation between the perceived level of professionalism and the sociodemographic characteristics of age, years of experience, and gender. However, nationality has been found to have a positive correlation with conflict and professionalism among nurses. Likewise, there is evidence indicating that there is no statistically significant correlation between overall conflict and the relationship between nurses and their clients, doctors, and health allied members. The outlook on nursing as a profession showed weak association with conflict. As the subscales of interpersonal, intrapersonal, and intergroup conflict increases, the level of professional outlook also increases. Additionally, it shows a correlation between intergroup conflict and job position of nurses. This highlights the importance of staff nurses and nursing management to comprehend the impact of professionalism in mitigating conflicts and taking proactive measures to resolve them before they escalate. This emphasizes the significance of reinforcing personal and leadership development, organizational training, and proactive conflict management frameworks that can enhance the overall organization.

Keywords: Conflict; Professionalism; Nurses

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Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Introduction

Conflict often emerges among individuals working together due to differences in needs, values, and interests. This opposition serves as a pivotal moment wherein an individual struggle with both vulnerability and strength while striving for either success or failure.

According to Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, the concept of "conflict" represents an important point in which individuals experience a simultaneous sense of vulnerability and resilience as they strive to achieve or encounter setbacks. Intrapersonal, interpersonal, intragroup, and intergroup conflict can be classified. Before a few years ago, research exclusively concentrated on individual workplace conflicts. However, the study of conflict and professionalism is noteworthy, considering the rapid transformation of the healthcare industry. In their study, Mosadeghrad and Arezoo, (2019) discovered that hospital managers experienced a higher degree of conflict due to organizational factors compared to personal factors. Conflicts that arise within hospital settings, characterized by behaviors such as verbal aggression, blame attribution, derogatory language, and rule violations have been observed to diminish the motivation levels of nurses. This decline in motivation subsequently exerts a negative impact on the quality of patient care provided.

Miscommunication is one of the main reasons work gets interrupted, productivity drops, and projects fail. Hence, workplace conflict management is very important. To deal with these situations, staff should be taught how to solve them,

nurses should know the policies and procedures for dealing with them, and everyone should know the right chain of command.

All employees must behave professionally in the workplace, according to the common definition, nursing professionalism usually requires knowledge, skills, and a good attitude. Professional values and ethics serve as the fundamental principles that underpin the nursing profession, guiding all aspects of professional practice. According to Poorchangizi et al., (2019), the profession of nursing upholds several fundamental principles such as generosity, independence, respect for the dignity of others, truthfulness, and a just society. These principles are outlined in *The Essentials of Baccalaureate Education for Professional Nursing Practice* (2016). The concept of conflict and professionalism in a highly diverse environment, such as our hospital, has emerged as a compelling area of study within the field of organizational management.

The majority of hospital workers are of different nationalities, and it is well known that misunderstandings or conflicts can arise when people from various backgrounds must work and interact together. According to Speights et al., (2020), the social contexts of work and family affect how people feel, and actively managing emotions is not always a bad thing and helps people maintain relationships. Therefore, the establishment of a physically and mentally healthy nursing staff is dependent upon healthcare managers safeguarding the capacity of their nursing staff to perform their duties, as well as the presence of a shared obligation to maintain a sustainable workforce. Furthermore, it is crucial to carefully consider the job requirements and job resources about the age of the nurses when implementing effective management interventions (Van der Heijden et al., 2019). They are most directly affected, and their profession can be physically and emotionally exhausting. In the realm of healthcare,

various factors such as ethnic background, sexual orientation, gender, citizenship, physical disability, and socioeconomic status exert influence on matters of representation, acceptance, and advancement, both within the context of healthcare and beyond (Stanford, 2020). Every employee has an exceptional way of handling situations, and they respond differently. Thus, the study includes a sociodemographic profile, which is a major aspect of the study that should be carefully evaluated. It may demonstrate and determine how nurses handle conflict on the job, and these factors may also influence their professionalism.

Since the researcher has been a quality nurse at one of the institution's facilities for approximately eight years, staff conflict and unprofessionalism have increased. One of the behavior problems was a bedside nurse arguing with a unit manager over an unfair patient assignment. Other problems included staff nurses refusing to take care of a difficult patient and a senior employee yelling at junior employees, which got in the way of the nurses' work. The new head nurse and another senior head nurse argued and fought about the patient's transfer. These problems are reported to the direct manager, who must investigate them and make a plan of action. If the conflict is not resolved, it is escalated to the Executive Nursing Administration and then to the Human Capital Department. All of these should be addressed as urgent issues by nursing management. This study was intended by the researcher out of an aspiration to contribute to the identification and relationship of the levels of conflict and professionalism as well as the necessity to solve this rising problem.

Background of the Study

In a hospital setting, a conflict-free environment is essential. However, conflict cannot be avoided. Statistics on workplace conflict are difficult to gather because they are sometimes concealed in data on high employee turnover, sickness rates, and grievance complaints (Jones et al., 2019). However, the researcher has observed the inevitable escalation of conflict in the hospital, and failure to identify and address this issue might have negative consequences, including difficult-to-resolve unprofessional behavior by nurses. Several examples of workplace conflict were seen, such as a doctor yelling at a midwife and calling her incompetent, a pharmacist and a nurse arguing over a missing prescription and threatening to report each other to their managers, and coworkers who avoid and don't talk to each other at work because of personal problems, from the past. Unfair workloads and allocations, such as a senior nurse assigning severe workloads to a novice nurse, result in complaints and transfer requests between a nurse and unit management. Unacceptable behaviors such as yelling or shouting from both parties are also demonstrated during some instances in the unit. Unfortunately, due to the high demand for work and a shortage of staff, conflict in the workplace is increasing, but it can be resolved and de-escalated with the right tools and management.

Undoubtedly, the mental health of employees can be profoundly influenced by the workplace environment (Grailey et al., 2021). Numerous factors contribute to workplace conflict, including personality differences, attitudes, ambiguity in roles, and breakdowns in communication. The hospital has an existing grievance committee, a workplace conduct policy, and an opportunity reporting system that encompasses all behavioral types, including power abuse, position abuse, communication,

interpersonal skills, and unprofessionalism. Staff nurses need to know about the program that is meant to protect them from conflict at work. However, not all employees are aware of these, and there are no programs or training about conflict and professionalism for staff nurses. However, by recognizing the gap, hospital administrators and policymakers will have a better idea of how to create a conflict management framework and a better way to deal with and handle similar situations at work. Therefore, it is imperative to evaluate the level of perceived conflict and professionalism among the nurses within the hospital, as well as their interpersonal dynamics.

The research study will aid in the development of new conflict resolution strategies or the revision of a current approach to protect or promote professionalism in the workplace. Discover new styles and techniques by fostering open-mindedness and transparency and by empowering employees to "Speak Up." Therefore, a conflict could be easily overcome by addressing the issue, managing the conflict, and portraying professionalism.

The link between conflict and professionalism needs further study as it lacks the current setting and literature that could help address this challenge.

Statement of the Problem

Conflict, its nature, and management are all defined differently by nurses in the hospital, as well as a varying levels of professionalism in the workplace. As a result, disagreement leads to an inefficient and ineffective workflow. Regardless of the structure and management in place, there are very several incident reports and

feedback on such issues. As a result, unresolved disagreement and underreporting in the system are noticeable, and statistical evidence does not support these occurrences. The numerous types of workplace conflict that can damage relationships and have a direct impact on patient safety are a challenge for nurses.

One problem is that there are insufficient incidents that are being reported. This could mean that staff are not aware of problems that need to be managed or merely ignoring them. It could also mean that staff feel unsafe or unsupported by supervisors and are afraid to report because they think they will be punished.

If a link can be established between the level of conflict and professionalism, it may be possible to consider methods for reducing conflict and implementing innovative and successful strategies to preserve professionalism in the hospital. Measuring the nurses' perceptions of conflict and professionalism would enable the researcher to recognize the perceptions of each staff nurse as well as how to manage conflict in an acceptable manner to establish a harmonious workplace with excellent teamwork and enhance collaboration. Therefore, the hospital may avoid more conflicts and enmity between its employees by acknowledging and identifying conflict and misunderstanding in the workplace. Further issues were minimized, and staff satisfaction also improved.

The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Sociodemographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Years of experience

1.3. Nationality

1.4. Gender

2. What is the level of perceived conflict among nurses working in the hospital in terms of:

2.1. Interpersonal conflict

2.2. Intrapersonal conflict

2.3. Intragroup conflict

2.4. Intergroup conflict

3. What is the level of perceived professionalism among nurses working in the hospital, in terms of:

3.1. Outlook on nursing as a profession

3.2. Job Position of the Nurse

3.3. Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.

4. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of conflict and the perceived level of professionalism among nurses working in the hospital?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of conflict and the sociodemographic profile (age, years of experience, nationality, gender) of the respondents?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of professionalism and the sociodemographic profile (age, years of experience, nationality, gender) of the respondents?

Significance of the Study

The present study extended the body of knowledge related to conflict and employee behavior concerning professionalism in the workplace. The study focused on determining the significance of the relationship between the perceived level of conflict and the professionalism of nurses. Moreover, the research study will be beneficial to the following:

Nurses. The benefit of the study is to promote awareness of their perception of conflict. It will make nurses more aware of the sources of conflict that they may be called upon to manage professionally and help nurses identify appropriate conflict resolution strategies that work best for them. It will enlighten nurses on the reality of their environment and be well educated about conflict resolution and management. It will also encourage nurses to say what they think and feel while still maintaining a professional attitude at work. It may also support nurses in strengthening their relationships with coworkers and other healthcare professionals.

For hospital and nursing service administrators the research study is important in the field of hospital management because it will give nursing directors and nurse managers relevant baseline information about how nurses see the relationship between conflict and professionalism. The research study will also help improve organizational productivity in the future and show that encouraging people leads to a

better way of managing a conflict-free environment through a culture of a harmonious, nonpunitive, and supportive workplace, especially here in the Arab country. Thus, the findings of the study and its recommendation will make the workplace better, raising the quality of care, and it might even generate attention for further research.

The research will raise awareness among the hospital's leaders and will be able to find ways to increase organizational productivity through highly engaged employees and addressing conflict in the hospital. It is also important for administrators, who will get a better idea of what should be emphasized in the organization to improve nurses' performance and reduce work disruptions.

The administrative body holds the capacity to effectively address and manage issues such as project failure, absenteeism, disengagement, and turnover. A comprehensive understanding, particularly of the managers, is essential for effectively implementing varied methods and skills in a manner that fosters a positive workplace environment, promotes harmonious relationships among colleagues, and ultimately enhances staff satisfaction, all without resorting to punitive measures.

This study will also be beneficial to new leaders in learning how to properly handle conflicts among staff that require resolution and conflict management and be able to empower nurses to give their opinions and ideas to participate in decreasing conflict in the workplace.

Nursing Educators. Educating the nurse or providing in-services, which can be included in the orientation, will help empower nurses on what they should do professionally because nurses have the fear of losing their jobs if they are involved in a conflict.

The educator's role in the study's conclusion is important because they help nurses by teaching and encouraging them to use the opportunity reporting system, and the proper channeling, and be aware of the escalation process if they run into problems at work that can't be solved.

This will also help in the aspect of conducting in-services focusing on conflict and crisis management and effective communication skills. In this manner, such a situation will be immediately resolved and not lead to a more serious problem such as aggression or bullying. It is also relevant that topics be discussed during the general nursing orientation about handling workplace conflict and being aware of policy and procedure if a situation arises.

Patients. They are directly beneficiaries of the study because, with a pleasant attitude in the workplace and a healthy environment, the nurse is more likely to display her high degree of professionalism by providing the best quality of patient care. The study will foster open communication, which is the foundation of healthy relationships, and will ultimately promote staff and patient satisfaction.

Researcher. The study will assist in identifying crucial aspects of nurses' perceptions of conflict and professionalism, leading to better knowledge and approaches to conflict in the workplace while preserving professionalism. In a highly diversified situation, it can be advantageous to be able to recognize these variables more readily. This can contribute as a guideline to the improvement of conflict resolution strategies and staff development programs and the study findings could serve as a foundation for future research on determining the relationship or influence after the COVID-19 pandemic on the conflict of professionalism in the workplace and other studies of a similar nature. Through the study of the correlation between nurses'

viewpoints on conflict and professionalism, the outcomes of this study can contribute to the advancement of knowledge and facilitate a deeper comprehension of the hospital's culture, free of conflict, as well as the enforcement of professionalism.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This descriptive and correlational study was done in one of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia's tertiary hospitals. The study commenced in March 2021 and was completed in May 2021. The scope of the study included registered nurses employed for more than 6 months at all levels of nursing job positions.

The primary objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive description of sociodemographic variables, including age, years of experience, nationality, and gender. Additionally, the study aims to evaluate the level of perceived conflict and professionalism and examine the potential association between these variables. This study does not encompass additional variables, such as marital status, educational level, and job position, which could have been relevant to consider. Nonetheless, the study solely incorporated the identified variables.

This was implemented in only one tertiary hospital in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Therefore, the result cannot be generalized to all facility areas and all hospital staff nurses in Saudi Arabia.

The researcher utilized the correlational study design to find connections between the variables. However, the research cannot determine the causal relationship among the studied variables. Another limitation is that the study was

conducted during a pandemic, and the condition may have aggravated the level of conflict and professionalism among nurses.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

The objective of this section is to perform a literature review on the topic of the perceived level of conflict and professionalism among nurses. The literature review was conducted using various academic databases, including Science Direct, PubMed, ProQuest, EBSCO, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The present study focuses on the utilization of specific keywords, namely Conflict, Professionalism, Interpersonal Conflict, Intrapersonal Conflict, Intergroup Conflict, Intragroup Conflict.

This section provides an overview of the relevant literature and studies that have contributed to the researcher's understanding and knowledge of the subject under investigation. This section offers information on establishing the research direction, selecting appropriate statistical tools, and providing guidance for writing the findings, conclusions, and recommendations. A substantial body of research has been conducted on the topics of conflict and professionalism as distinct areas of study. Nevertheless, there is a limited number of published literary works that delve into the complex relationship between conflict and professionalism within the nursing profession.

Conflict

According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, the term "conflict" refers to an important difference of opinions or interests among individuals or groups, often leading to intense and contentious debates. Conflict, as defined by Piryani and Piryani (2019),

refers to an internal disagreement or a divergence of opinions or disputes among individuals that possess the capacity to result in negative consequences.

Conflict encompasses four distinct dimensions, namely interpersonal conflict, intrapersonal conflict, intragroup conflict, and intergroup conflict. This concept is elaborated upon in a study conducted by Black et al. (2019), wherein they define "conflict level" as the quantitative measure of individuals engaged in the conflict. Conflict can arise between individuals, groups, or organizations, involving a single individual, two individuals, two or more groups, or two or more organizations. This phenomenon could potentially influence the factors contributing to conflicts as well as the methods employed for their resolution.

Conflict is an unavoidable occurrence that can manifest in various professional contexts within the hospital setting, including the nursing profession, which experiences a widespread prevalence of such conflicts globally. Interactions may occur within various cohorts of healthcare professionals, among diverse healthcare team members, across different groups of healthcare professionals, or between patients and any member of the healthcare team. Conflict significantly impacts the proficiency, self-assurance, and morale of healthcare practitioners.

Conflicts within intricate healthcare organizations have a substantial impact on the quality of healthcare services and present significant staffing challenges. The level of conflict and the workplace environment influence nurses' ability to practice professionalism in nursing (Al-Hamdan et al., 2014). Thus, collaboration between nurses and physicians, two essential occupational groups in healthcare, significantly impacts the performance and efficiency of healthcare delivery (Delak & Širok, 2022).

Unresolved conflict at work can lead to a high turnover rate and make it harder for people to contribute and work well together.

According to Moeta and Du Rand (2019), inadequate conflict management is a prominent factor contributing to reduced productivity, diminished morale, and financial detriment within organizations. According to popular opinion, the primary factors contributing to conflicts among professionals include issues related to leadership, compensation, job delineation, communication, and emotional intelligence. According to Mohammed et al. (2022).

The presence of diverse cultures and beliefs has the potential to exacerbate conflicts among members of healthcare teams, families, and patients. According to Sinskey et al. (2019), To optimize the provision of comprehensive care to various patient populations, it is imperative to cultivate a healthcare workforce that mirrors the diversity observed within our communities, encompassing factors such as ethnic background, gender, sexual orientation, citizenship, physical disability, and socioeconomic status. According to Stanford University (2020).

In the contemporary healthcare environment, the significance of effective communication cannot be overestimated, as it serves as a fundamental element. Conversely, inadequate communication has the potential to result in conflict among healthcare professionals. The responsibility for identifying the underlying cultural reasons for conflict, selecting an appropriate strategy, and intervening resides with the manager. Moreover, a comprehensive collection of ethnographic studies encompassing 59 distinct cultures (Garfield et al., 2020) revealed that the predominant cross-cultural role of leaders was the resolution of conflicts. This finding was observed in 78% of the cultures included in the sample.

The key element of a conflict is found not in its mere existence, but rather in its effective management. According to Piryani and Piryani (2019), inadequate handling of the situation can lead to unfavorable outcomes and hinder progress. Conversely, effective handling of the situation can foster healthy competition, acknowledge valid disparities, and serve as a potent catalyst for motivation.

Interpersonal Conflict

Interpersonal conflict, or relationship conflict as it is sometimes called, is "a dynamic process that happens when people have negative emotional responses to what they think is a difference of opinion" (Barki and Hartwick, 2004; as cited by Lavelle et. al., 2022), it means interpersonal conflict occurs when two people disagree. For instance, you can argue with a coworker about a shared problem.

According to Parvaresh-Masoud et al. (2021), interpersonal conflict can be characterized as a relatively moderate manifestation of aggressive behavior. The manifestation of workplace hostility can take on various forms, ranging from overt behaviors characterized by direct rudeness towards a coworker to more covert actions such as the dissemination of rumors about a colleague. This occurs as a direct consequence of rivalry and conflict over available resources. For people to stay in touch with each other, they must build relationships, and when these relationships change, which happens often, it can lead to conflict. (Donohue & Cai, 2022). The occurrence described is frequently observed within the hospital environment, a complex phenomenon. Gaining insight into this conflict will facilitate the creation of efficient healthcare systems and the formulation of conflict interventions tailored to nursing (Freedman, 2019).

Interpersonal conflicts are unavoidable because people interact with each other. They may result from issues with communication, discrepancies in activities, an unsuitable organizational environment, or different points of view (Sompa, 2015). Kim et al. (2017) say that the main effects of interpersonal conflicts are a hostile work environment and poor teamwork.

Another study stated that unresolved conflict among healthcare professionals can affect patient care. This means that the conflict needs to be solved before it affects the quality of care (Cavar and Petrak, 2018; cited by Dahshan & Moussa, 2019). One finding of a study conducted in Algeria was that 72% of the nursing staff had experienced conflicts with peers during clinical hours (Lebrague & Benamar, 2020). It is supported by Gebiresilus et al. (2014) mentioning that interpersonal conflicts at work have direct effects on employees' mental and emotional health, indirect effects on employees and the organization's productivity, and can make it harder for nurses to give patients good healthcare. The present study's findings align with prior research, indicating a negative correlation between interpersonal conflict and organizational performance (Abugre et al., 2022).

One descriptive cross-sectional study included 202 Thai Nguyen University of Medicine and Pharmacy registered nurses, who rated their capacity to identify their own and others' emotions and moods as the greatest, but their ability to self-manage conflict-induced stress was ranked the lowest, followed by their ability to regulate their moods and emotions and their ability to negotiate (Long & Long, 2022). The report implies that conflict management skills seemed to be lacking, therefore emotional intelligence and negotiation are important areas to improve on.

A study conducted by Guerra et al. (2011) in the Rio Grande do Sul region employed an exploratory and descriptive research approach. The study utilized a qualitative interpretative method and focused on five hospital institutions with a minimum capacity of fifty beds. The participants in the study were nurses who held positions as nurse managers or were engaged in related roles for a minimum duration of four years. The results show that internal conflict is the key concept for managers, and they must deal with it every day. They also perceive conflict as something terrible and harmful that should be avoided. On the other hand, most of the nurses said they had problems with other people. Incompatibilities between people are also the most difficult to deal with.

Other research was conducted in Egypt with 200 nurses as respondents, showing 73.5% of whom believed themselves to be involved in interpersonal conflict and 26.5% of whom were conflict-free. The same was true of the questionnaire survey conducted in a hospital in the Midwest, which revealed a positive and significant association between interpersonal conflict and verbal aggression. However, neither interpersonal conflict nor teamwork is significantly associated with physical violence. (Arnetz et al., 2018).

According to Vivian et al. (2019), nurses working in units characterized by interpersonal conflicts, or a lack of support may require assistance in enhancing their communication skills, empathy, and teamwork abilities. Gaining insight into the underlying determinants that influence our actions, both in personal and professional contexts, facilitates the development of comprehensive solutions that address the fundamental causes.

It shows that interpersonal conflict does contribute to the stress of nurses, which is sometimes an added burden to them mentally, it may trigger misbehavior, bad attitude, and hostility towards others. Therefore, the mental health of staff nurses is also important to consider and should also be addressed by having time to listen to their concerns and let them speak up.

Intrapersonal Conflict

Intrapersonal conflict refers to a psychological phenomenon that arises within an individual when they are confronted with two or more incompatible demands (Dahshan & Moussa, 2019).

Resolving intrapersonal conflict necessitates the individual's ability to choose among various alternatives (Arafat et al., 2018). Thus, it is a conflict within oneself when decision-making must be executed and there is a dilemma between what should be done and what is desired because if it is not met it causes dissatisfaction within the self, which is similar to one of the findings of a survey conducted in two states, including Haryana and Punjab, where 716 responses were analyzed to conclude that intrapersonal conflict and insufficient effort have a substantial positive relationship with life dissatisfaction. (Punia et. al., 2021). Constant values, religious views, and upbringing drive it. Individual conduct generally reflects the objective laws of the surrounding environment (Higazee, 2015). Awareness of intrapersonal conflicts can contribute to the creation of change from within the individual, overcoming challenges and, thus, developing personal development and cultivating a deeper and more resilient sense of self (Rifkind & Picco, 2014).

A qualitative exploratory study was done to find out where nurses' feelings of success in helping patients come from, what they mean, and how they work. It was

found that nurses find it hard to accept unhealthy patient behavior because it goes against their ideas of good care and health. Nurses define success as "keeping on course," "considering their job," and "protecting themselves." These three items are interrelated. (Duprez et al., 2020). Managing intrapersonal conflict is essential for building internal peace within a person, and for conflict transformation and resolution (Redekop, 2014). To understand the entirety of an individual, intrapersonal conflict must be addressed, identifying the root causes of conflict, which most frequently originate within the individual (Silverman, 2020). The respondents of a research study identified several specific manifestations of intrapersonal conflict. These included difficulties in self-understanding and relating to others, a negative self-image, challenges in staying grounded in the present moment, an inability to recognize personal boundaries, and various other personal characteristics (Iuliana & Alexandra). Therefore, intrapersonal conflict in decision-making in the workplace is a common factor of personal experience influencing one's behavior and action in a certain situation, and as a result, the hospital should help such as counseling services or employee assistance programs to relieve personal tension or intrapersonal conflict.

In accordance with research findings, intrapersonal characteristics, such as self-efficacy, also influence personal goals (Rampullo et al., 2015). Analyzing intrapersonal conflict can provide the opportunity for growth and reflection, although the conflict can bring emotions that contribute to uncomfortable feelings toward the emerging conflict (Hocker et.al, 2021).

It can be difficult for staff nurses to adjust to the new environment and obstacles that they face while working in a different nation. As a result of these factors,

intrapersonal conflict may develop. On the other hand, having a greater capacity to control it could assist reduce the adverse effects that are typically linked with it.

Intragroup Conflict

In the field of sociology, the phenomenon of intragroup conflict, alternatively referred to as infighting, pertains to conflicts that arise among two or more individuals within a cohesive group. Conflicts may arise within a group for a variety of reasons, including insufficient support, the emergence of new issues necessitating changes in group member roles and relationships, or enforcement of values and responsibilities within the group (Forsyth, 2009; Dahshan & Moussa, 2019). Due to diversity in the workplace and misunderstanding among employees who work within the group, intragroup conflict develops (Evans, 2017). About the role of intragroup conflict, a study found that burnout is positively associated only with conflict related to personal issues or relationships. This aligns with previous research on workplace conflict, which has consistently shown that relationship conflicts can have negative effects. One study specifically found that nurses reported experiencing a moderate level of conflict (Leon-Perez et al., 2016). Several authors have discovered a connection between relationship conflict and negative emotional reactions that contribute to an escalation of conflict. This escalation is characterized by increased behaviors of mutual hostility (Leon-Perez, Medina, et al., 2015).

Based on a separate study, it has been found that the most common types of conflict that nurses encounter in the selected institutions are intragroup conflict among nurses and disruptions caused by physicians. A study conducted in Saudi Arabia found that nurses had a low perception of professionalism. The study also revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between intragroup conflict and

this perception. This information was cited by Zakari et al. (2010) and mentioned by Dahshan and Moussa (2019).

According to sociodemographic data, only hospital type influences nurses' conflict experiences (Higazee, 2015). Large hospitals with a lot of nurses in a department or organization often have problems between the nurses.

Additionally, a meta-analysis research study found a negative relationship between relationship conflict, process conflict, and group outcomes. This finding contradicts the results of De Dreu and Weingart (2003), who did not observe a strong and negative association between task conflict and group performance (De Wit et al., 2012). However, it is worth noting that an additional study suggests that an increased degree of intricacy in nursing care is associated with elevated levels of conflict within nursing units. Moreover, this elevated intra-group conflict has been found to contribute to heightened job stress and diminished job satisfaction (Almost, 2010). The conclusion of one of the studies is that moderate degrees of conflict boost performance because they encourage critical thinking and innovation in decision-making toward goal achievement. Yet, excessive degrees of disagreement diminish patient care performance in the research findings. (Tebitendwa, 2022). It indicates that team dynamics are significant in the workplace, and as a result, enhancing relationships and fostering efficient communication are essential for maintaining harmonious relationships, eliminating conflict concerns, and promoting a stress-free work environment it is also recommended that management techniques for resolving disagreements be at a high level to enhance patient care.

According to Ayranci (2020), the study's participants observed notable variations in their perceptions of intragroup conflict, which were influenced by their

perceptions of shared leadership. Those in favor argue that the communal aspect of shared leadership leads to alterations in the way individuals perceive conflicts within their respective groups. These statements provide further explanation regarding the potential for simultaneous conflicts within a group to have multiple underlying causes.

Intragroup conflict arises among team members within the same department, reflecting complex group dynamics across all organizational levels, which can manifest as both task-related and interpersonal conflicts. The cultivation of emotional intelligence among team members is essential, as it enables them to respond constructively to intragroup conflict, allowing for effective management and expression of emotions that lead to positive dispute resolution (Antunes et al., 2012). Various factors contribute to these differences, and research has shown that conflict within management groups can significantly impact overall group performance and outcomes. Additionally, intrapersonal and intragroup conflicts can indirectly affect the productivity of individuals and the organization as a whole (Saridi et al., 2019).

Intergroup Conflict

Intergroup conflict refers to a state of disagreement that arises between two or more distinct groups. The concept of diversity in the workplace has been likened to a double-edged sword, as it possesses the capacity to yield both advantageous and detrimental outcomes (Chrobot-Mason & Aramovich, 2013). Interorganizational conflict can be seen in disputes between two organizations in the same industry. In any work setting, nurses face different levels of conflict.

A well-managed intergroup conflict enables the discussion of difficulties, with each party being encouraged to express their thoughts, resulting in the recognition of

possible solutions that enhance organizational performance (Saaksvuori et al., 2011). Intergroup transactions are permissible between group representatives who represent their group's interests and not their own, and on behalf of their group (Richter et al., 2005).

Intergroup conflict commonly emerges when two distinct divisions exhibit discordance in their objectives or the allocation of resources. The complexity of intergroup conflict arises primarily from the large number of individuals involved. An "us-against-them" mindset becomes apparent as various factions form alliances.

According to Yue and Thelen (2023), one current study found that verbal aggression led to relationship conflict within the work group, which in turn increased employee perceptions of work-life conflict. It indicates adverse work conditions and is associated with individual and group variables.

The primary factors contributing to conflict within multicultural teams commonly include hierarchical structures and cultural dimensions, alongside decision-making processes, divergent communication styles, and linguistic differences. According to Redhead et al. (2021), ethnographic data indicates that conflict resolution is commonly associated with prestige-based influence, rather than coercive dominance-based influence, across various cultures.

The study conducted by Reed & Nelson (1989) investigated the relationship between social networks and conflict in a sample of 20 organizational units. Organizations characterized by minimal conflict exhibit a higher prevalence of intergroup strong links, which are defined as frequent and regular interactions, compared to organizations marked by high levels of conflict.

One qualitative study conducted in a general hospital reveals the intergroup conflict scenario and the complex connection between physicians and administrators, which leads to initiatives targeted at boosting hospital performance. The study indicates that the efficacy of collaboration between physicians and administrators is associated with the adoption of quality initiatives and hospital performance (Klopper-Kes et al., 2011).

The intergroup conflict ultimately influences a more diverse group. According to research, social identity and intergroup connections that are expressed through power, control, status, and competitiveness are significant (Hewett et al., 2009). The findings indicate that communication is the most crucial factor, and if a conflict between departments emerges, it should be addressed at a higher level of management because it is more complex than an individual dispute.

Professionalism

The concept of professionalism can be defined as the comprehensive understanding and application of the various responsibilities, characteristics, interpersonal dynamics, attitudes, and role-based behaviors that professionals are expected to possess and exhibit in their interactions with both individual clients and society as a whole.

Professionalism is characterized by a set of essential qualities and behaviors required for individuals in a specific field. These qualities include a deep understanding of the subject matter, a curious and inquisitive mindset, accountability for one's actions, the ability to work independently, advocacy for the best interests of clients or stakeholders, a commitment to innovation and forward-thinking, effective

collaboration, and adherence to ethical principles (Fantahun & Demessie et al., 2014). High levels of professionalism enhance the quality of nursing practice, promote job satisfaction among nurses, increase autonomy and empowerment, and facilitate organizational citizenship behaviors (De Braganca & Nirmala, 2017). By demonstrating knowledge and behaviors aligned with regulatory standards and nursing guidelines, nurses can exemplify professionalism, which is critical for successful clinical practice (Tanaka et al., 2014, as cited in Bekalu & Wudu, 2023).

Nursing professionalism encompasses a collection of values, discipline, and morale that guide and fortify nursing practice. Utilizing nursing professionalism, conflict can be managed positively, contributing to growth and positive change in the organization. Therefore, conflict resolution is accomplished best (Chang et. al., 2017). This crucial element empowers nurses to deliver care of the utmost quality to patients. Furthermore, nurses must engage in professional communication with the public to foster the flourishing of the nursing profession (Skela-Savic, 2016). The establishment and cultivation of professionalism in the nursing field is of utmost importance, as the actions and behaviors of nurses play a pivotal role in safeguarding patient well-being and fostering public confidence in the nursing profession. However, there is no universal agreement on what constitutes nursing professionalism. The Professional Practice Framework documents of nursing regulators serve as a valuable resource for identifying the constituent traits of professionalism that are thematically related.

The perception of low professionalism among nurses can be attributed to a range of factors, both related to the workplace environment and the personal backgrounds of the individuals. These factors include nurses' interest in their profession, as well as the views of families, society, and consumers (Zakari et al.,

2010). Furthermore, additional research suggests that perceptions of professionalism may be negatively impacted by various influences, including nurses' experiences, commitment to the nursing profession, and the perspectives of families, clients, and society regarding professionalism (El-Hosany, 2017). Being professional corresponds to the concept of professionalism in nursing literature and hospital guidelines, where the best qualities of a nurse are portrayed and their best conduct at work is required. Regardless of whether they are in a stressful position, they must have a professional demeanor to respond to any challenges they may face. A nurse must develop the ability to maintain professionalism during adversity. Using the proper tools, intergroup conflicts in the healthcare workplace can be viewed as an opportunity for growth and beneficial outcomes (Ifeanyi & Babangid, 2020).

Outlook on Nursing as a Profession

A study conducted by Weerheim, et. al. (2019). Healthcare institutions have undertaken tests that have explored varying levels of autonomy in diverse fields, including individual empowerment and the implementation of self-management teams. The experimental outcomes have exhibited varying levels of achievement. Nurses employed in self-managing teams within diverse healthcare organizations have reported experiencing heightened levels of motivation and job satisfaction. This enables nurses to preserve their professionalism in nursing practice by determining the method of conflict resolution that is most appropriate for the given situation. In the realm of medical practice, conflict is unavoidable, and frequently, nurses find themselves in the center of the conflict (Simpao, 2013). Professional values in nursing include the maintenance of patients' confidentiality, meeting the health needs of a culturally diverse population, safeguarding the right to privacy of patients, and

maintaining competency in nursing practice (Fisher, 2014). At the center of the promotion of the nursing profession is the internalization and acquisition of values that become standards in guiding behavior and nursing practice (Poorchangizi et al., 2019).

In recent years, autonomy and a good professional image have become important topics for hospital organizations for nurses. However, one research stated that attributes to autonomy, innovation, and vision were at the lowest levels. (Atsede and Asrat, et. al., 2014). A qualitative study was conducted to investigate the standards of nursing professionalism. The study identified several themes that emerged from the data, including the promotion of empowerment, adherence to ethical principles and professional commitment, the availability of resources and a supportive organizational structure, and the need to address social status disparities. According to Ravani Pour et al. (2014), the factors that influence individual abilities and professionalism, human values and professional ethics, educational and organizational structure, resources, as well as internal and external factors are significant in academic contexts. Furthermore, there exists a noteworthy positive association between nursing professionalism and nurse image. Various factors that impact nursing professionalism include nurses' temperament, professionalism, career aspirations, the portrayal of nurses' roles, and foundational practical experience in nursing (Cho and Kim, 2014).

Hassandoost et al. (2016) utilized the "Hall's Professionalism Inventory" (HPI) scale to evaluate professionalism. The results indicated a moderate level of professionalism, with higher scores observed in autonomy and a relatively lower sense of calling it "high." Furthermore, there is a significant correlation between the age and

years of experience of nurses and their level of professionalism. Nevertheless, a negative impact has been recorded as well.

A cross-sectional study was conducted to investigate the factors contributing to the inconsistent brand image observed within the nursing industry. The study identified several key factors that influence this phenomenon, including the diverse range of education and credentials among nurses, the relatively low priority placed on cultivating a strong brand image, the absence of comprehensive leadership development programs, the lack of professionalism exhibited by some individuals within the profession, portrayals of nurses in the media and online platforms, patients' personal experiences with nurses, how nurses are treated by their professional colleagues, and the influence of gender roles on the perception of nursing. These findings shed light on the multifaceted nature of the factors that contribute to the inconsistent brand image within the nursing industry. The study conducted by Godsey et al. (2020) is of particular interest in the field. A cross-sectional study has revealed that the inconsistent brand image of the nursing industry is influenced by various factors, such as diverse education and credentials, a lack of prioritization of image, and insufficient research on the connections between structural empowerment, workplace incivility, and nurses' intentions to leave their organization. Furthermore, it has been found that structural empowerment has a significant direct negative impact on supervisor incivility, coworker incivility, and nurses' intentions to leave their organization (Yürümezolu & Kocaman, 2019). Another study appears to have the same negative result, in which compassion satisfaction was influenced by factors of professionalism like burnout and secondary traumatic stress (Bahani et. al. 2022). The nursing profession is characterized by a higher likelihood of attrition due to two primary

factors: the prevailing negative public perception of nurses and a lack of professional recognition within the workplace (Al Yami & Watson, 2014).

According to Ravani Pour et al. (2014), the empowerment and enhancement of nursing professionalism are influenced by various factors, including the importance of education, continuous assessment and evaluation of nursing skills and knowledge, the role of nursing in the health care system, and the social status of nursing. Nurses must be given greater significance and better treatment. Any hospital or organization should prioritize staff satisfaction with the advantages and rewards of their work, as well as respect and appreciation from employers, as these aspects influence nurses' perceptions of their profession, hence affecting nurse turnover and retention (Aljedaani, 2017). They will be better prepared to upgrade their skills and knowledge through continuous education and training, which will help to boost their confidence and improve their public image.

Job Position of the Nurse

A function within an organization is referred to as a job position. It includes both day-to-day responsibilities and long-term goals. Every nurse at the hospital is assigned a certain position, and that position comes with a set of duties and obligations that are designed to contribute to the hospital's overall accomplishments. A role refers to the expected behavior of an employee, and each person inside an organization has one or more roles that they are required to fulfill. Being a nurse has been established during the university days and nursing competency encompasses fundamental skills and capabilities that are essential for effectively carrying out the responsibilities associated with the nursing profession. Hence, it is crucial to precisely delineate nursing competency in order to establish a solid framework for the nursing education

curriculum (Fukada, 2018). This will foster critical thinking ability for independent nursing roles, providing them confidence in giving exceptional care (Lasebikan et al., 2012).

Professionalism in job performance is associated with increased commitment, high-quality patient outcomes, and job satisfaction of nurses; therefore, the agreement of respondents that their job position permits them to maintain professionalism in daily nursing practice achieves the desired care delivery outcomes (De Bragancaa & Nirmala, 2017). The job position of nurses provides them with role clarity that increases their perceptions of professionalism and stability of job performance and increases psychological empowerment among nurses (Hossny et. Al., 2020). These elements include a job title, a description of responsibilities, and an agreement between the employee and the organization. With the skills developed in nurses' job positions, comprehensive care is delivered to clients, providing safe, competent, and ethical care across all healthcare settings (Suresh, 2013). Nurses are obligated by professional standards to critically evaluate their roles within their occupational context, which functions as a framework for their conduct in the field, thereby guaranteeing the provision of care at an optimal standard (Alidina, 2013). Manager-subordinate conflict may arise when there is ambiguity regarding the specific function of the subordinate and each party holds a distinct interpretation of that role (Whetten & Cameron, 2012).

According to Tanaka et al. (2016), "The Behavioral Inventory for Professionalism shows that Nursing Managers scored highest on professional behaviors of incompetence and continuing education and lowest on publication and communication and revealed that higher professionalism in nursing is significantly

related to higher nursing experience, higher educational levels, and job position as a nurse administrator."

A research study conducted in the Philippines has revealed that the leader-member exchange is strongly associated with employee satisfaction, as well as the demonstration of citizenship behaviors. Furthermore, it has been observed that a low level of workplace conflicts is perceived in organizations where the leader-member exchange is prominent. Additionally, a significant negative correlation has been found between leader-member exchange and workplace conflicts (Ufitinema & Sausa, 2016). So, when a group leader and a group member talk to each other, it makes it easier for workplace conflicts to be less intense. Trust is built in the immediate ward environment, and the role of the line manager has a big impact on it. Professionalism and dedication to the nursing profession are good qualities that can build trust. On the other hand, new management ideas, practices, and styles overseen by managers hired from the private sector can have a negative impact (McCabe & Sambrook, 2014). The perception of social support by clinical nurses moderates the intensity of emotional labor and positively improves nursing performance. The study's findings suggest that nurse managers should prioritize enhancing the professionalism and social support of nurses, as well as fostering working environments that encourage greater engagement in emotional labor, to enhance nursing performance. This research contributes to the recognition by nurse management of the influence of emotional labor, professionalism, and social support on nursing performance. More research is required to design programs that increase the clinical nurses' professionalism, provide social support, and reduce emotional labor. (Koh et al., 2018). With job positions, nurses believe their tasks to be well defined, are aware of

the organization's expectations, and are therefore better equipped to provide high-quality care (Allemeh et al., 2013; Mohamed & Hosny, 2020).

Relationship of the Nurse to the Client, Doctors, and Other Health Allied Members

Patients can only participate in their care when there is mutual trust and respect between them and the nursing team. During patient admissions, nurses and patients should develop a positive relationship to encourage patients' participation in their nursing care (Atakro et al., 2019) because if there's a lack of professionalism it can have adverse effects not only on individuals but also on institutions and the services they offer. Moreover, the quality of patient care is heavily reliant on the conduct and competence of nurses and physicians, (Terzioglu, Temel, & Uslu, 2016).

The discourse surrounding health care in the United States often revolves around issues such as patient autonomy, patient-centered care, the utilization of evidence-based approaches, and the management of costs (Lathrop, 2013). In the change effort, the nurse must feel encouraged, be able to communicate effectively, and yield control. To participate in the empowerment process, the client must be motivated by change and possess the necessary skills. Throughout the entirety of the participation process, both the healthcare professional and patient must be active participants. This involvement encompasses a variety of actions and procedures (e.g., shared decision-making, taking part in focus groups, and representation in official bodies, (Molina-Mula & Gallo-Estrada, 2020).

Collaborating with patients is often regarded as the most rewarding aspect of a nurse's profession, despite the challenges and conflicts that may arise in the

workplace. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize improvements in services that focus on optimizing the organizational factors that enhance nurses' interactions with patients (Bridges et al., 2013). To deliver effective care that meets the therapeutic needs of patients, it is crucial for nurses to develop relationships that are both goal-directed and strategically planned with clients and healthcare professionals (Canadian Nurses Association, 2019).

In contrast, nurse-patient interactions should not prioritize altering the patient's beliefs and practices. Instead, nurses should assume the role of observers, witnessing the experiences of patients and their families as they navigate health and illness patterns (Molina-Mula & Gallo-Estrada, 2020). The relationship between nurses and physicians significantly influences conflict and professionalism within the healthcare setting. Nurses strive to maintain professional boundaries and relationships to ensure the delivery of high-quality care services (Canadian Nurses Association, 2017). A substantial number of nurses report experiencing interpersonal conflicts with professionals from other disciplines, particularly with physicians. This type of conflict is notably more prevalent among experienced nurses in managerial roles (Lahana et al., 2019). It is suggested that overly hierarchical and rigid administrative structures, along with the regulatory frameworks governing nursing practice, contribute to a lack of autonomy among nurses (Shanaz et al., 2020).

A study conducted revealed that there are noticeable group disparities within doctor and nurse teams, indicating a potential lack of mutual awareness regarding the respective levels of participation, the amount of work, duties, and contributions to the overall level of care. The presence of these disparities has been observed to potentially result in feelings of frustration, conflicts, suboptimal collaboration, and

jeopardized patient safety. However, upon identification and within specific boundaries, these differences can be harnessed to facilitate the creation of interventions aimed at enhancing teamwork, (Morag & Zimmerman, 2021).

In addition, a survey conducted in Lebanon reveals that there is no significant difference between the degrees earned by nurses and the participants' years of experience, and one-fourth of physicians oppose the notion that nurses should be considered collaborators or colleagues (Ahmadiéh et al., 2019). Therefore, it implies that there are still some doctors who do not see nurses as their partners in the workplace. But changes may still happen, and hospital nurses will create and make sense of their proficient parts in organizational situations.

A separate qualitative analysis revealed that the implementation of team-based collaboration with other healthcare teams, specifically pharmacists, was associated with a higher burden for nurses and a reduction of partnerships with pharmacists. The quantitative data analysis findings confirmed the validity of these results, as they demonstrated statistically significant decreases in perceived collaboration (Bryant et al., 2018). A clinical setting with distinctive divisions contributes to either the struggle or the test of professional behavior and may enormously influence the relationship concerning collaboration and support from other departments. The delivery of multi-professional inpatient rehabilitation is complex.

Age, Years of Experience, Nationality, Gender

Nurses receive education that emphasizes the importance of taking into account social determinants of health, including but not limited to revenue, gender, racial or ethnic background, job opportunities, and schooling. When

accompanied by higher levels of education, years of experience enable nurses to advance in professional ranks that develop the required competencies in the management of work-related conflicts (Al-Hamali et al., 2013). This education equips nurses with the necessary knowledge and skills to serve as crucial advocates in facilitating the connection between community resources and the delivery of healthcare services to individuals in their respective work and living environments (Lathrop, 2013; Olshansky, 2017). Role conflict can be affected by gender, which impacts the actions of individuals (Al-Hamali et al., 2013) and women can perceive collaboration as needed in individual work styles and tend to be more supportive managers, while men can view work as completed independently in the absence of assistance from others and are more direct (Hahn & Litwin, 2015).

According to one study a high level of professionalism can be associated with the gender of nurses. As men and women develop behavioral variations based on emotional and physical factors, professional perspectives might vary (Scott, 2015). There can be a statistically significant difference in the utilization of strategies for conflict resolution based on the gender of nursing personnel (Dikmen et al., 2016; Hamali et al., 2013). Younger nurses may employ an avoidance strategy to resolve disputes because they are worried about the repercussions or lack the necessary expertise (Iglesias et al., 2012).

Lahana et al. (2019) provides further evidence supporting the idea that factors such as age, professional experience, education, and leadership roles significantly influence the choice of conflict resolution strategies. Research indicates that work-related disputes tend to decrease with age, as older individuals typically exhibit greater work maturity and mutual respect (Akpabio et al., 2015). Their findings specifically

indicate that younger nurses, who have limited responsibilities and insufficient training in conflict management, are more likely to resort to avoidance as their primary strategy. Additionally, other studies have shown that the impact of work-related conflicts on nursing roles and responsibilities lessens with age, as nurses acquire the necessary skills for conflict resolution (Akpabio, 2015). According to Al-Sudani et al. (2013), the nursing profession prioritizes achieving positive health outcomes and ensuring client satisfaction. Therefore, it is essential for nurses, regardless of their level of experience, to demonstrate professionalism in their daily clinical practice.

In addition, a separate study conducted an evaluation of professionalism levels among Korean American registered nurses (RNs) by employing Hall's Professionalism Inventory (HPI) scale. The study also investigated various factors that were linked to professionalism, including the individual's current nursing position, employment status, workplace conditions, overall number of years of experience in nursing in the United States, where they obtained their degree completion, and the length of nursing education in the United States. According to Kim-Godwin et al. (2010), the results indicate that professionalism among nurses is influenced by various internal and external factors. These findings contribute to a broader comprehension of the patterns of professionalism within an international context. Fantahun et al. (2014) conducted an institutional-based cross-sectional study in North Ethiopia, and there was a significant correlation observed between the age of the respondents, their work experience, and the level of professionalism.

Rengin (2018) found that younger nurses experience higher job stress levels than their older counterparts, with newly graduated nurses reporting the greatest stress. In contrast, nurses with over five years of experience tend to exhibit improved

conflict management skills and greater job satisfaction (Wai-Tong & Yin, 2016). Additionally, as both age and years of nursing experience increase, so does appreciation for professionalism. More experienced nurses are better equipped to fulfill their job roles and are less impacted by work-related conflicts affecting their performance (Akpabio et al., 2015).

The majority of the results were in line with a previous study conducted on 774 American registered nurses who exhibited high levels of professionalism, were affiliated with professional organizations, and possessed extensive nursing experience. However, no statistically significant differences were observed in the conflict resolution approaches employed by medical and nursing staff members (Alshammari et al., 2017). In contrast to the findings, the present study revealed that diploma nurses exhibited higher levels of professionalism compared to individuals holding a degree or a master's degree. This finding contradicts the previously mentioned results (Wynd, 2003).

In summary, several different countries have undertaken comprehensive literature reviews about the subjects of conflict and professionalism. A great deal of study has been undertaken about conflict and professionalism, yielding diverse viewpoints and significant findings across various dimensions. As a result, it proved beneficial to investigate one of Saudi Arabia's tertiary hospitals involving respondents from diverse national backgrounds. Furthermore, it is imperative to possess an understanding of the nurses' perceptions regarding conflict and professionalism, as this knowledge will contribute to enhancing the general climate of work and leadership within the hospital.

Within an enormous organization, nurses are expected to be highly qualified and to always keep their nursing professionalism, despite the influence of external work settings such as heavy workload demands and a high volume of perceived workplace conflict. Research on conflict and professionalism in Saudi Arabia is limited; so, this review investigates the additional knowledge regarding the relationship between professionalism and conflict and provides empirical evidence to address this gap.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study.

“Theory of Reciprocal Determination of Environment, Person, and Behavior”

By: (Bandura, 1986)

Bandura (1986) proposed the Theory of Reciprocal Determinism, which highlights the interdependent relationship between the environment, individual characteristics, and behavior. In the context of nursing, this theory can be applied to understand the dynamics between the level of conflict and professionalism.

The environment, such as the workplace setting, organizational culture, and leadership style, can significantly influence the professionalism displayed by nurses, affecting how they handle conflicts. For example, a supportive and well-structured work environment may promote higher levels of professionalism, enabling nurses to manage conflicts more effectively. Conversely, a stressful or poorly managed environment might increase conflict levels and diminish professional behavior.

Individual characteristics, such as a nurse's experience, emotional intelligence, and personal values, also play a crucial role in determining how they respond to conflict and exhibit professionalism. Nurses with higher levels of professionalism may approach conflict with a problem-solving mindset, maintaining composure and ethical standards. On the other hand, those with lower levels of professionalism might find conflicts more challenging and may struggle to manage them constructively.

Finally, behavior, in this case, the way nurses engage in or respond to conflict—can influence both the environment and individual characteristics. High levels of conflict in the workplace may create a tense atmosphere that negatively affects professionalism, while professional behavior can help mitigate conflict and promote a healthier work environment. These components, environment, individual characteristics, and behavior are constantly influencing each other in a reciprocal manner, illustrating the dynamic interplay between conflict and professionalism in nursing.

Bandura's theory is relevant to this study as it is based on the principle of reciprocal determinism, which posits that an individual's behavior is shaped by a continuous interaction between the environment and personal factors. In this context, individual factors, including sociodemographic profiles, are crucial in understanding

behavior. The theory suggests that a person's actions are influenced by their cognitive processes, personal characteristics, and their reciprocal relationship with their surroundings. As a result, individuals are seen as both shaped by and actively shaping their environment (Bandura, 1986). This perspective aligns with the study's focus on how the level of conflict and professionalism among nurses is influenced by their environment and personal factors.

According to the theory of reciprocal determinism, a person's behavior is influenced by both their social environment and individual traits. This relationship operates through cognitive processes and external social stimuli. Physical characteristics such as age, height, gender, and appearance can provoke various responses from the social environment (Lerner, 1982). Consequently, demographic factors can impact conflict and professionalism in nursing. Observable traits may affect how nurses respond to pressures in a hospital setting, influencing behaviors like role conflict. This interaction determines which environmental repercussions, such as workplace conflict, arise and how they are managed. Individual experiences within a sociocultural context can vary based on personal perspectives or changes in the work environment, ultimately shaping how nurses handle different types of conflict—interpersonal, intrapersonal, intragroup, or intergroup. This, in turn, affects their professional interactions with patients, colleagues, and superiors, potentially influencing the overall organizational climate.

This theory enhances the study by providing insight into the correlation between conflict and nurses' opinions of their professional conduct. It emphasizes the impact of organizational culture on the nursing environment, affecting nurses' perceptions of conflict and their capacity to manage it proficiently. These considerations subsequently

influence their professional nursing practice. The theory assists the researcher by offering a framework for the continuous collection of data, enhancing the comprehension of the correlation between perceived conflict levels, professionalism, and the sociodemographic characteristics of nurses in a tertiary hospital in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of the Study.

The present study employs the "Relationship Model of Workplace Conflict and Professionalism" to clarify a streamlined framework encompassing the concepts and variables under investigation. This framework delineates the interconnections between these elements and the directionality of their impact. The dimensions of conflict among nurses and its association with professionalism, as well as the potential influence of sociodemographic profiles of the nurse respondents, are indicated by the model dimensions.

As represented in the model, nurses face workplace disputes in the healthcare working environment, which is unavoidable because nurses establish work

relationships with organization employees and disagreements emerge as a result of those relationships. The model focuses on workplace conflicts in the dimensions of interpersonal conflict, intrapersonal conflict, intergroup conflict, and intragroup conflict, considered as independent variables of the study.

The presence of conflicts among nurses has been observed to have a strong correlation with professionalism, which is widely regarded as a crucial factor in the development of professional nursing standards and the delivery of nursing services of exceptional quality. Professionalism among nurses focuses on the aspects of outlook on the nursing profession, job position, and the relationship of nurses with members of the healthcare system, considered as dependent variables of the study. Workplace conflicts and professionalism among nurses can be influenced by their sociodemographic profile in terms of age, years of experience in the organization, nationality, and gender.

An analysis is performed on workplace conflict variables and the sociodemographic profile of nurses, significantly influencing professionalism in the provision of quality clinical services. Figure 2 presents the conceptual framework of the study.

Research Hypothesis

1. There is a significant relationship between the perceived level of conflict and the perceived level of professionalism among nurses working in the tertiary hospital.

2. There is a significant relationship between the perceived level of conflict and the respondents' sociodemographic profile (age, years of experience, nationality, gender).

3. There is a significant relationship between the perceived level of professionalism and the respondents' sociodemographic profile (age, years of experience, nationality, gender).

Operational Definitions

For this research, the following terms are defined operationally:

Conflict refers to the disagreement occurring in the workplace in terms of interpersonal, intrapersonal, intergroup, and intragroup and this is evaluated by using Perceived Conflict scale (PCS).

Interpersonal conflict refers to the disagreement occurring between two or more individuals.

Intrapersonal conflict refers to the disagreement or troubles occurring within one's self.

Intragroup conflict refers to the disagreement between members of the same group or team.

Intergroup conflict refers to the disagreement between two or more groups such as other departments.

Nurses refer to all nurses employed in the hospital working for more than six months.

Professionalism refers to the conduct, behavior, and attitude of a nurse in terms of outlook on the nursing profession, job position of the nurse, and relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members by using the Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (VCNS).

Outlook on Nursing as a Profession refers to the general attitude and nurses' point of view.

Job Position of the Nurse refers to the role of nurse either as a bedside nurse or managerial post.

The relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members refers to the behavior and attitude towards each other.

Years of Experience refers to the duration of professional experience accumulated by an individual while employed as a nurse within a hospital setting.

Age refers to the time of life at which some particular qualification, power, or capacity arises or rests (merriam-webster dictionary.com). In this study it refers to Less than 30 years old, 30-39 years old and 40 years old and above.

Gender refers to the behavioral, cultural, or psychological traits typically associated with one sex (merriam-webster dictionary.com). In this study, it refers to male and female.

Nationality refers to people having a common origin, tradition, and language and capable of forming or actually constituting a nation-state (merriam-webster dictionary.com). In this study, it refers to staff nurses coming from Philippines, India, Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Pakistan, South Africa, Malaysia, Palestine.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational design to investigate the relationship between variables. The present study aims to quantitatively assess and establish the associations between the independent, dependent, and confounding variables. The confounding variables encompassed various sociodemographic factors about the participants, including age, years of experience, nationality, and gender.

Conflict and professionalism have been cited as independent entities in a few published studies. Unfortunately, the literature on the association between these two variables is inadequate. Hence, the principal goal of this investigation is to examine the correlation between perceived levels of conflict and the professionalism exhibited by nurses. This inquiry holds importance as it pertains to the nurse's welfare, the overall work environment within hospitals, and the safety of patients.

Sampling Design

The total number and formal list of eligible participants were secured from the office of the Director with the approval of the Head of the Nursing Research Committee and the Executive Director of Nursing (EDON). This study used a simple random sampling design wherein the probable participants were selected randomly utilizing a random number generator application.

The study focused on a specific target population, namely nurses who had been employed for six months or longer at a tertiary hospital located in Riyadh, which is situated in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The total population of the nurses in the tertiary hospital was comprised of N=3324 nurses at the time of the study.

The inclusion criteria involved registered nurses who consented to participate in the study, regardless of their job position, age, gender, or nationality. It also includes all registered nurses with a diploma degree, bachelor's degree, or postgraduate degree such as a master's. The researcher excluded nurse educators, nurse interns, and nurses who belong to other departments outside of nursing administration.

The study is also limited only to one of the tertiary government hospitals in Riyadh, which does not give a generalization of the study.

The determination of the sample size was carried out utilizing Slovin's formula, as outlined by Galero-Tejero in 2011. The analysis assumes a proportion variability of 0.05 and a confidence level of 95%. Thus, the sample size computed was 357 nurses of the hospital. However, the actual sample size was increased to 500 people because it was expected that some participants would drop out or not answer. The determination of the sample size is of utmost importance in assessing the representativeness of the data concerning the entire population. Consequently, it can be inferred that an increased sample size typically leads to heightened precision.

All eligible respondents (n = 500) were given questionnaires. Only N=483 nurses returned the completed surveys; 10 did not answer, and 7 were incomplete, which were not included in the data analysis. Giving a response rate of 96.6 percent and an attrition rate of 3.4 percent. The attrition rate observed in this study appears to be potentially associated with a lack of interest in participating, apprehension towards

addressing workplace conflict-related questions, or the presence of personal factors influencing their decision to withdraw from the study.

Research Setting

This research was conducted in one of the tertiary hospitals in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, a CBAHI (Saudi Central Board for Accreditation Of Healthcare Institutions, JCI (Joint Commission International) accredited, tertiary government hospital also known as a training center with the most up-to-date medical equipment, fully equipped facilities, and high-level medical facilities. The research focused on all the hospitals and medical centers, which have a capacity of 1200 beds. Annually, the hospital serves an estimated 30,000 inpatients and 500,000 outpatients.

The research setting was chosen because the hospital has nurses from a wide spectrum of cultural, geographical, and educational backgrounds that spend a broad amount of their days interacting with coworkers, other department staffs, doctors, and patients, which makes the hospital a suitable location for this study.

The hospitals and centers are listed below.

- 1 Main Hospital
- 2 Children's Specialized Hospital
- 3 Women's Specialized Hospital
- 4 Rehabilitation Hospital
- 5 Ambulatory Department

- 6 Critical Care Center
- 7 Emergency Department
- 8 National Neuroscience Institute
- 9 King Salman Heart Center
- 10 Comprehensive Cancer Center

Research Instrument

Data collection was conducted using two previously validated standardized instruments. English has been identified as the prevailing language for professional and formal communication within the healthcare system in Saudi Arabia, as noted by Almutairy, McCarthy, and Gardner in their study conducted in 2014, no translation of the survey was performed. This study's questionnaire was obtained from an open source, and no permission was necessary.

The Instrument was composed of three (3) sections: (1) The questionnaire gathers the respondent's sociodemographic profile. (2) Perceived Conflict Scale (PCS) by Gardner (1992); Huber (1996); and (3) Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (VCNS) by Valiga (1996). Section 1 gathers the sociodemographic characteristics of nurses included in the study, such as age, years of experience, nationality, and gender. Section 2 elicited the nurses' level of perception towards conflict. Section 3 obtained the nurses' level of perception towards professionalism.

These tools were utilized to correlate Level of Conflict (independent variable) to Level of Professionalism (dependent variable). Furthermore, the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants were considered as a potential confounding variable that could influence both the extent of conflict and professionalism.

Perceived Conflict Scale (PCS)

The Perceived Conflict Scale (PCS) is an occupation-specific tool that was originally devised by Gardner (1992) with the aim of examining the perceived levels and levels of conflict experienced by newly graduated nurses during their initial year of employment. Subsequently, Huber (1996) revised the scale in order to enhance its effectiveness and applicability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained in this study was 0.67, suggesting a satisfactory level of reliability.

The questionnaire consists of a series of 16-item statements that can be responded to using a 5-point Likert scale. The scale includes response options ranging from "strongly agree" (5) to "strongly disagree" (1). The PCS is organized into four distinct subscales, each focusing on different aspects of social interaction. These subscales include intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, and intragroup. The intrapersonal subscale comprises 4 items, the interpersonal subscale consists of 5 items, the intergroup subscale encompasses 4 items, and the intragroup subscale includes 3 items.

Questions 2, 8, 11, 15, and 16 of the survey tools were reverse scored when the subscale scores were computed. The calculation of mean scores for perceived conflict involved the summation of individual item scores, followed by division by the total number of items.

The participants were presented with five response option with the corresponding weight as follows:

Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Description
5	4.21 to 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41 to 4.20	Agree
3	2.61 to 3.40	Undecided
2	1.81 to 2.60	Disagree
1	1.00 to 1.80	Strongly Disagree

The construct of conflict Level pertains to the subjective perception of nurses within a given situation, wherein respondents are asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with a specific statement. The higher mean scores signify a greater perception of conflict among nurses in the hospital. This data was interpreted as: the higher the scores, the more the respondents agreed to the statements and the more they are aware of the conflict, its impact within themselves, others, and the organization. Therefore, a score of 5 (strongly agree), fully aware and understands conflict in the workplace, 4 (agree) are those who are aware, 3 (neither agree/disagree) is unsure and minimal understanding of the conflict situation, while 2 (disagree) and 1 (strongly disagree) are those who are unaware or do not know about conflict. The computation of the mean score and standard deviation per subscale was conducted to provide a descriptive analysis of the perceived level of conflict among nurses working in a tertiary hospital located in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

The scores were Interpreted by Individual subscales. To conceptualize the meaning of the scores, and mean scores are interpreted as follows: less than 3 is low level of perception and above 3 is high level of perception.

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale

The Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale is a tool utilized for the purpose of evaluating nurses' perceptions of professionalism.

The survey instrument comprises a total of 25 items designed to assess the nurses' perspective on nursing as a profession. Specifically, 10 items pertain to the nurses' outlook, 8 items pertain to their job position, and 7 items pertain to their relationships with clients, doctors, and other health allied members. Respondents are asked to rate their agreement with each item using a 5-point Likert scale. The scale includes response options ranging from strongly agree (+2) to strongly disagree (-2).

The participants were presented with five responses with the corresponding weight as follows:

Scale	Range of Mean Values	Verbal Description
+2	1.21 to 2.0	Strongly Agree
+1	0.41 to 1.20	Agree
0	-0.39 to 0.40	Undecided/Neutral
-1	-1.19 to -0.40	Disagree
-2	-2 to -1.20	Strongly Disagree

The calculation of mean scores for perceived professionalism involved the summation of scores for each item within the respective subcategories, followed by division by the total number of items. The examination of the validity and reliability of the items comprising this instrument has been thoroughly investigated across multiple studies. Through the utilization of construct and criterion-related validity tests, as well as subscale reliability analysis, the obtained Cronbach's alpha coefficient was determined to be 0.79. This value signifies a substantial level of reliability, as indicated by Valiga in 1996.

In this present study, the higher scores indicate that nurses are fully aware and understand the perception of professionalism in the hospital, and a negative score represents they lack awareness or are not aware about professionalism. The overall mean value of each item variable of the perceived professionalism scores is interpreted into two levels: low perception with a score of below zero and high perception with a score above zero.

Data Collection Procedures

Figure 3. Procedure for Data Collection.

Figure 3 shows the research process from the study proposal, approval, and data collection and interpretation. The researcher obtained official permission from the Nursing Research Committee for conducting this study in the hospital. The proposed study was additionally submitted to the Institutional Review Board of the hospital and the University of the Philippines—Open University by the researcher. Following a few revisions, the study received approval to proceed with the research process. After the researcher has sent all the approval to the chairperson of the Nursing Research Committee. She informed all the nursing directors of the data collection and sought their support. The researcher proceeded to the offices of the Director of Nursing in order to obtain a comprehensive roster containing the names of the proficient nurses

who have been employed at the hospital for a duration exceeding six months. Then, simple random sampling is utilized with the help of the random number generator application to determine the participants from the hospitals. The questionnaires were distributed to the participants by the primary investigator, or in cases where direct distribution was not feasible, they were delegated to the head nurse or unit manager according to the predetermined schedule for the selected participants.

Samples were contacted by the researcher to ensure acknowledgment of the questionnaires, secure informed consent, and for follow-up purposes. The researcher maintained an open line of communication with the samples to answer tool-related queries. The duration of the collection was two months, so it was personally followed up every week for a better response rate by encouraging staff participation.

The eligible participants were provided with an introductory letter that outlined the objectives of the research, identified the principal investigator, and detailed the measures implemented to safeguard the participants' anonymity and confidentiality. A consent letter was attached to the introduction letter. Each participant's informed consent and survey were numbered starting from 1 and ending with the last number to ensure all documents were received. The participants were instructed to give the head nurse or unit manager the sealed envelope. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. 17 participants refused to answer the questionnaires due to personal reasons. The chosen participants were approached with permission from the unit managers during their duty and were asked to complete the questionnaire at their most convenient time after informed consent was secured. To ensure participant confidentiality, each participant received an individual identifier. In the database in which the data are stored, no names were used in the surveys. The data access was

restricted to the individual who possessed the necessary authorization to conduct data analysis. Furthermore, all data sets were securely stored within a locked cabinet. Exclusive access to the personal information of the participants was granted solely to the researcher. Upon the lapse of a three-year period subsequent to the conclusion of the investigation, the gained data shall undergo a process of shredding and subsequent destruction.

Data Analysis and Management

The quantitative data analysis was conducted utilizing the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Data analysis is the process of providing objective evidence to support assertions about the relationships between variables and to test the viability of hypotheses (Neuman, 2005; Salkind, 2005). The sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents were described using descriptive statistics, specifically frequency and percentage. The mean was used as a statistical measure to ascertain the response score of the participants in relation to their perceived level of conflict and professionalism. The association or relationship among quantitative variables was determined through the utilization of Pearson correlation analysis and chi-square test statistics.

Table 1*Matrix Table for Data Analysis*

Objective	Study Variables	Level of Measurement	Statistical Treatment
1. What is the sociodemographic profile of nurses working in the hospital? In terms of:	Confounding Variables 1.1 Age 1.2 Years of experience 1.3 Nationality 1.4 Gender	1.1 Age-ordinal 1.2 Years of Experience-ordinal 1.3 Nationality-Nominal Gender-Nominal	Frequency Distribution and Percentage
1.1 Age 1.2 Years of experience 1.3 Nationality Gender			
2. What is the level of perceived conflict among nurses working in the hospital? In terms of:	Level of Perceived Conflict scale (Independent Variables) in terms of: 1. Interpersonal conflict 2. Intrapersonal conflict 3. Intragroup conflict 4. Intergroup conflict	Interval	Mean and Standard Deviation (SD)
2.1 Interpersonal conflict 2.2 Intrapersonal conflict 2.3 Intragroup conflict 2.4 Intergroup conflict			

3. What is the level of perceived professionalism among nurses working in the hospital?	Level of perceived professionalism (Dependent Variables)	Interval	Mean and Standard Deviation (SD)
<p>In terms of:</p> <p>3.1 Outlook on nursing as a profession.</p> <p>3.2 Job Position of the Nurse.</p> <p>3.3. Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.</p>	<p>In terms of:</p> <p>1. Outlook on nursing as a profession.</p> <p>2. Job Position of the Nurse.</p> <p>3. Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.</p>		
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of conflict and professionalism among nurses working in the hospital?	Relationship between the perceived level of conflict and professionalism	Subscale scores – Ratio	Pearson Correlation

Ethical Consideration

The researcher demonstrated a commitment to upholding the principles of anonymity, privacy, and confidentiality, recognizing their significance as both legal and ethical imperatives (Whitehead et al., 2007). Privacy refers to the systematic measures taken to safeguard the identity of participants, a crucial aspect in enhancing anonymity. In this study, the researcher implemented a method wherein each participant's questionnaire was assigned a unique numerical code, thereby ensuring increased confidentiality. Additionally, participants were explicitly instructed that they had the option to refrain from answering any questions that made them feel uneasy.

In order to ensure the utmost confidentiality, the researcher implemented a robust measure by furnishing each participant with a securely sealed envelope. This envelope served as a designated repository for the completed questionnaires, effectively mitigating any potential apprehensions on the part of the participants regarding the preservation of their anonymity. The questionnaire pack contained detailed instructions outlining the necessary steps for completing and returning the sheets.

To further ensure confidentiality, exclusive access to the data was granted solely to the researcher. The data will be retained for a duration of up to three years subsequent to the completion of the study. The physical documents will undergo a meticulous shredding process before being disposed of.

The ethical principle of beneficence is also one of the significant issues that refers to the Hippocratic oath "be of benefit, not harm." According to Beauchamp and Childress (2001), "the principle of beneficence includes the professional mandate to do good and According to Ford L. and Reutter L. (1990), "important research is to

serve our constituents better and promote their welfare." Respondents will be requested to be approached about the study, and they will be able to respond to the researcher at their own convenience.

In conducting research, informed consent is the primary ethical consideration and should never be coerced. As the guiding principle of research ethics, it is important that the people who are asked to take part in the study understand the purpose, benefits, and risks, as well as the purpose of the study, their freedom of choice, their anonymity, and how to get in touch with the researcher. Armiger (1997) says, "It shows that a person gives permission willingly, knowingly, and with intelligence." By completing the application for ethical review form and providing the required documentation, ethical approval was duly obtained from the University of the Philippines Open University, ensuring compliance with established ethical guidelines and protocols. Furthermore, the necessary documentation was completed in order to obtain ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board of the hospital. The researcher diligently sought ethical approval prior to the commencement of data collection.

The researcher's cover letter detailed this study's procedure. This study was voluntary; no personal identifiers were collected, ensuring participant anonymity and confidentiality. Respondents were instructed that completing the questionnaire will result in the inclusion of an informed consent form. All respondents were notified that they could withdraw or decline participation at any moment. Sufficient time was provided to complete the questionnaire as well, and no patient was involved in this research.

The study diligently followed inclusion and exclusion criteria during participant selection, ensuring that individuals from various social and economic backgrounds were considered. This approach aimed to prevent any potential exploitation or discrimination against vulnerable populations. Individuals who exhibited a lack of willingness to participate or voluntarily withdrew from the study were not subjected to any form of judgment. The individuals who opted not to participate and those who willingly took part in the study were all offered due respect for their beliefs, behaviors, and cultural backgrounds. The participants were explicitly informed that their decision to participate or not would have no bearing on their evaluation or prospects for promotion.

The selection of participants for this study was guided by a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria. These criteria were carefully designed to ensure that the respondents chosen would provide valuable insights into the nature of conflict and professionalism within the workplace. By including individuals who meet these criteria, we aim to enhance our understanding and expand our knowledge in this area of research. The individuals who took part in this research did so on a voluntary basis. The participants were given the opportunity to exercise their freedom of choice in deciding whether to engage in the study. If individuals opt out of participation, it is important to note that the provision of services at this establishment will persist without alteration.

The researcher had not foreseen the occurrence of any physical or physiological harm among the participants. The potential occurrence of anxiety, discomfort, or embarrassment among participants during the process of responding to the survey questions is regarded as a minimal risk that can be reasonably expected.

The study necessitates the complete engagement and allocation of time from the participants. The participants have been assured that the preservation of confidentiality regarding their responses will be upheld throughout the duration of the study. In the hypothetical scenario where the participant experiences ongoing discomfort, they possess the right to cancel their engagement in the study and opt out of the questionnaire at any given point in time.

Respondents will not receive any direct benefits from the study; rather, their participation will be of significant contribution in answering the objective of this study and serving the purpose of improving the overall quality of healthcare services. In addition to this, it was made clear to the respondents that they may approach the researcher with a request to have access to the study results at any time.

Respondents received no monetary compensation from the study. In the same way, the researcher conducted this study as a mandatory requirement of her master's degree program without obtaining any financial support from external institutions or organizations.

The study was carried out without any commercial or financial affiliations that could be perceived as a potential conflict of interest.

The researcher considered no direct potential impact of the research on society; however, it has taken steps to ensure that the findings are communicated clearly and effectively to the public.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this chapter, the analyses and interpretations are discussed. The results of the statistical tools utilized are presented in tabular format, which corresponds to the sequence of the Chapter 1 research questions.

I. Respondent's Sociodemographic profile

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage distribution of sociodemographic profile (n=483)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Less than 30 years old	70	14.5
30-39 years old	258	53.4
40 years old and above	155	32.1
Years of Experience		
Above 6 months – 1 year	50	10.4
2-4 years	111	23.0
5-9 years	151	31.3
10-14 years	114	23.6
15 years and above	57	11.8
Nationality		
Saudi Arabia	26	5.4
India	106	21.9
Philippines	328	67.9
Jordan	9	1.9
South Africa	6	1.2
Pakistan	4	0.8
Malaysia	3	0.6
Palestine	1	0.2
Gender		
Male	89	18.4
Female	394	81.6

Age

According to the data presented in Table 2, it can be observed that a significant proportion of the participants fall within the age bracket of 30 to 39 years old, with 258 respondents, or 53.4%; 155 respondents, or 32.1%, are in the range of 40 years and above; and the smallest group of 70 respondents are in the age range of less than 30 years old, or 14.5%.

The study demonstrates that most participants were adults who are capable of managing their personal feelings and are more likely to experience workplace conflicts and job stress. To address workplace issues effectively, greater problem-solving, confrontation, and negotiation skills are required. The age of the respondents may also be associated with fewer workplace disputes, as they are at a point in their careers where they are more satisfied with their positions. As a result, they have developed the capacity to manage workplace conflicts more effectively than younger nurses.

A study by Rengin (2018) found that younger nurses experience more job stress than their older colleagues, with newly graduated nurses facing the highest levels of stress. As nurses mature and learn how to resolve workplace issues, their roles and employment become less affected. Work-related disputes decrease with age due to increased work maturity and respect among older individuals (Akpabio et al., 2015).

Years of Experience

The results indicate that a significant proportion of the respondents have 5 to 9 years of experience in the hospital, with 151 individuals accounting for 31.3% of the sample. This is closely followed by 114 respondents, representing 23.6% of the sample, who reported having 10 to 14 years of experience. The third-largest cohort

consists of 111 participants, accounting for 22.9% of the total, who have a professional background spanning two to four years. Additionally, 57 respondents, equivalent to 11.8% of the sample, reported having 15 or more years of work experience.

According to the data, the majority of nurses in the hospital have been with the organization for a significant period, ranging from over 5 years to more than 15 years. Most of these nurses are from different countries, and working in Saudi Arabia presents an opportunity with good benefits, encouraging them to stay. Additionally, they value working in a hospital accredited by CBAHI (Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions) and JCI (Joint Commission International). This suggests that many of the nurses employed at the hospital have extensive clinical experience and are able to cope with the challenges of the workplace. This group likely possesses mastery of skills, procedures, and a high level of comfort in their roles.

This finding suggests that the hospital employs a substantial number of experienced nurses, offering greater opportunities for career advancement within the nursing profession, as well as providing a chance for nurses from different countries to work in a cutting-edge healthcare facility. It also demonstrates that nurses with many years of experience in the organization are less likely to encounter organizational conflicts, as they have developed essential conflict resolution skills. Alternatively, it may indicate that they tend to overlook such conflicts, having become accustomed to the work environment.

Respondents are expected to be able to effectively handle job stress, which contributes to workplace disputes, and hence to have a low level of perceived conflicts. According to a study conducted by Wai-Tong and Yin (2016), there is evidence to suggest that nurses who possess more than five years of experience in the field of

nursing demonstrate an enhanced ability to effectively manage organizational conflicts.

Furthermore, it is anticipated that these experienced nurses will also experience a greater level of job satisfaction within the nursing profession. More years of experience will provide nurses with the capability to perform job roles and be less affected by work-related conflicts in job performance (Akpabio et al., 2015). According to the findings of Alshammari et al. (2017), there is a lack of obvious disparity in the conflict resolution approaches employed by medical and nursing professionals, as supported by their extensive professional backgrounds.

Nationality

It presents the distribution of respondents according to nationality. Findings show that the majority of the respondents are coming from the Philippines, which ranked 1st with 328 respondents, corresponding to 67.9%, followed by the second biggest group of respondents from India, ranked 2nd with 106 respondents, or 21.9%. 26 respondents, or 5.4%, come from Saudi Arabia, which ranks 3rd. The small groups are: 9 respondents, or 1.9%, from Jordan; six respondents, or 1.2%, from South Africa; 4 respondents, or 0.8%, from Pakistan; three respondents, or 0.6%, from Malaysia; and the smallest group, with one respondent, 0.2%, from Palestine, ranked 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, and 8th.

The healthcare system in Saudi Arabia faces significant challenges, notably a shortage of local healthcare professionals. This reliance on imported healthcare workers, particularly from the Philippines and other countries, highlights the systemic need to attract skilled nurses to meet the growing demands for medical services.

The findings indicate that hospitals in Saudi Arabia actively employ nurses from various countries, motivated by several appealing factors. The country offers excellent living conditions, including access to free healthcare services and tax-free salaries, which are particularly attractive to expatriates. Moreover, the opportunity to work in a culturally diverse environment enriches their professional experience and personal development.

This reliance on foreign nurses suggests that a substantial number of staff nurses prioritize favorable working conditions when deciding where to seek employment. The combination of competitive compensation and benefits, alongside a supportive work environment, plays a crucial role in their choice to work in Saudi Arabia. Furthermore, given the escalating cost of living in many countries, these nurses perceive that remaining in Saudi Arabia offers them better financial stability and quality of life.

This dynamic raises important implications for healthcare policy and workforce planning in Saudi Arabia. To mitigate the ongoing shortage of local professionals, it may be necessary for the government and healthcare institutions to consider initiatives that improve the appeal of nursing careers for Saudi nationals. This could include investing in education and training programs, enhancing working conditions, and promoting the long-term benefits of a nursing career in the country. Ultimately, addressing these challenges is essential for building a sustainable healthcare workforce that can meet the needs of the population.

Gender

The hospital's nursing staff is predominantly composed of female individuals, as indicated by the majority of nurse respondents, with 394 respondents, or 81.6%,

and the rest are male, with 89 respondents, or 18.4%, which is fairly similar in other countries. This may be attributed to expatriates, who are the major respondents and are female nurses that were drawn to Arab countries due to the ease of employment, generous benefits, and secure working conditions. Respondents also have the opportunity to work in a dynamic, global, and technologically advanced work environment. The positive perception of the nursing profession that society promotes is also related to the findings. Physical and emotional factors may influence the actions and perceptions of work conflicts and professionalism of both men and women. Male nurses are more inclined to engage in aggressive behavior in conflict situations, whereas female nurses have a natural predisposition to maintain a calm work environment. As men and women develop behavioral variations based on emotional and physical factors, professional perspectives might vary (Scott, 2015). Women can perceive collaboration as needed in individual work styles and tend to be more supportive managers, while men can view work as completed independently in the absence of assistance from others and are more direct (Hahn & Litwin, 2015). Role conflict can be affected by gender, which impacts the actions of individuals (Al-Hamali et al., 2013).

II. Level of Perceived Conflict

Table 3

*Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Conflict of the Respondents
Interpersonal Conflict*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Another nurse often disagrees with each other about how work in this unit should be handled.	3.17	1.19
2	My supervisor and I usually agree with what my job is, and the requirements I must fulfil.	4.15	0.67
3	Patients often demand that I do things that I just cannot do.	3.11	1.12
4	When I do something that satisfies one person or group, other people are frequently upset with what I have done.	2.50	1.00
Overall Mean		3.23	1.00

Perceived Conflict Scale Interpretation:

5	High Level
4	High Level
3	High Level
2	Low Level
1	Low Level

The level of perceived conflict among nurses in the dimension of interpersonal conflict is presented in Table 3. Item 2 findings revealed a “high level” of interpersonal conflict among nurses and their superiors agreeing with the job and requirements that must be fulfilled, with the highest mean of 4.15. Item 4 was given the lowest mean of

2.50, which shows the “low level” of conflict among nurses regarding “doing anything to satisfy one individual, one group, or other people who are frequently upset with what nurses have done.” Another nurse often disagrees with the handling of work and patient demands to do things nurses cannot do, creating a “high level” of interpersonal conflict, with mean values of 3.17 and 3.11, respectively.

The grand mean of 3.23 indicates a "high level" of interpersonal conflict among nurses. The small standard deviation (SD = 1.00) shows that nurses had agreed the most and had the most similar answers. It represents that the majority of the respondents relatively have the same perception towards conflict and that interpersonal conflict is evident in the workplace. Based on the study results, there was a high level of interpersonal conflict reported among the nurses. This could be due to multinational employees, nurses, administrators, patients, and other professionals, which are the principal sources of conflict, and the hospital is characterized by a diverse array of interactions, conflicts, and interdependencies. The statement made is supported by the results obtained from a research investigation carried out in Algeria, wherein it was observed that 72% of the nursing personnel encountered instances of interpersonal disagreement with their colleagues while engaged in clinical duties (Lebrague & Benamar, 2020). Conflicts regarding nurses' job performance do occur at hospitals with colleagues and superiors, according to the findings. The assertion is supported by the results of a study conducted by Guerra et al. (2011), which suggest that conflict holds the highest degree of influence on managers and that managers themselves regularly encounter conflict during their daily responsibilities.

The hospital environment often presents a notable prevalence of conflict among nurses, which can be attributed to various factors. One prominent factor is the heavy workload that nurses face, particularly in tertiary hospitals that specialize in complex medical cases. Additionally, the daily interactions with diverse hospital staff from different nationalities can also contribute to the negative impact on the work-life balance of nurses. The primary effects of interpersonal conflict are a hostile work atmosphere and diminished teamwork (Kim et al., 2017). The presence of interpersonal conflicts within the workplace has been found to have a significant influence on the psychological and emotional well-being of employees. Additionally, these conflicts can have both indirect repercussions on employees and the overall productivity of the organization. Furthermore, it has been observed that such conflicts can detrimentally affect the ability of nurses to deliver high-quality healthcare services to patients (Gebiresilus et al., 2014). Interpersonal conflicts are inevitable due to human relationships and can take the form of communication problems, discrimination of activities, an unsuitable organizational environment, and differences in perceptions (Sompa, 2015).

In the hospital, there are employee manuals and policies in place, but there is a lack of understanding and awareness; therefore, they are ineffective. Continuing education in conflict management is crucial for facilitating the implementation of policies aimed at enhancing the provision of healthcare services. This educational intervention is expected to have a facilitating impact, promote effective conflict resolution strategies, and ultimately lead to improved healthcare delivery.

Table 4*Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Conflict of the Respondents:**Intrapersonal Conflict*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
5	My obligations to my work frequently conflict with my obligations to my family, friends, or myself (outside the job).	2.50	1.12
6	I often cannot get equipment, supplies, or medications when I need them.	2.68	1.08
7	I often have too many things to do at one time.	3.43	1.05
8	I usually agree with the decisions my supervisor makes.	3.72	0.80
9	My patients often make requests or need care that I feel I should provide but cannot because I lack the time or energy.	2.87	1.12
Overall Mean		3.04	1.03

Perceived Conflict Scale Interpretation:

5	High Level
4	High Level
3	High Level
2	Low Level
1	Low Level

The level of perceived conflict among nurses in the dimension of intrapersonal conflict is presented in Table 4. In item 8, findings revealed a “high level” of intrapersonal conflict among nurses, with nurses agreeing with superiors’ decisions, with the highest mean of 3.72, and too many things to do at one time, with a mean score of 3.43. In items 5, 6, and 9 with “low level,” it shows that nurses’ work obligations are frequently in conflict with family and social obligations; the inability of nurses to get equipment, supplies, or medications; and a lack of time and energy to fulfill patients’ requests, with mean values of 2.50, 2.68, and 2.87, respectively.

The calculated grand mean of 3.04 indicates a high level of intrapersonal conflict among nurses. This is further supported by the homogeneity of responses, as evidenced by the standard deviation of 1.03. The presence of a small standard deviation suggests that there is minimal variation in the responses of nurses regarding their experience of internal disputes caused by frustration or anxiety when faced with specific tasks or decisions within the hospital setting.

The findings showed that respondent nurses have a high level of intrapersonal conflict. This may be due to nurse respondents experiencing personal challenges and an underdeveloped capacity to overcome fear when utilizing ways for resolving intrapersonal conflict. Personal conduct tends to reflect the objective laws of the surrounding environment (Higazee, 2015).

This finding implies that the majority of respondents who come from a different background and different upbringing lacked the ability to choose between options when confronted with conflicts, between what should be done and what is desired. It can be attributed to their care for themselves and cultivation of inner peace, as either they do not wish to or they do not have the capacity to. In accordance with research findings, intrapersonal characteristics, such as self-efficacy, also influence personal goals (Rampullo et al., 2015).

Intrapersonal conflict occurs within the person, in which the individual requires selection of alternatives in resolving intrapersonal conflict (Arafat et al., 2018). Considering the varied conflicts often originate internally within the individual, management of intrapersonal conflict is vital for the nurses, thereby enabling them to manage intrapersonal conflict to a low level. Managing intrapersonal conflict is essential in building internal peace within a person for conflict transformation and resolution (Redekop, 2014). To understand the entirety of an individual, intrapersonal

conflict must be addressed, identifying the root causes of conflict, which most frequently originate within the individual (Silverman, 2020). Analyzing intrapersonal conflict can provide the opportunity for growth and reflection, although the conflict can bring emotions that contribute to uncomfortable feelings towards the emerging conflict (Hocker & Wilmot, 2021). Awareness of intrapersonal conflicts can contribute to the creation of change from within the individual, overcoming challenges, thus developing personal development and cultivating a deeper and more resilient sense of self (Rifkind & Picco, 2014).

Table 5

*Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Conflict of the Respondents:
Intragroup Conflict*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
10	I frequently encounter problems when I transfer my patients to other units or departments.	2.65	1.00
11	I usually agree with the way other nurses think things should be done on this unit.	3.49	0.85
12	Many times, the things that support services are supposed to do are not adequately done, and I either must argue with another unit, or do someone else's job.	2.96	1.01
13	I am unable to provide adequate patient care because of the time that I spend dealing with hospital rules.	2.78	1.10
Overall Mean		2.97	0.99

Perceived Conflict Scale Interpretation:

5	High Level
4	High Level
3	High Level
2	Low Level
1	Low Level

The level of perceived conflict among nurses in the dimension of intragroup conflict is presented in Table 5. In Item 11, findings revealed a “high level” of intragroup conflict among nurses, with nurses agreeing with other nurses on work to be done in the unit, with the highest mean of 3.49. Nurses frequently encounter problems when patients are transferred to other units; support services are not adequately done; and the inability of nurses to provide adequate patient care is perceived as a “low level,” with mean values of 2.65, 2.96, and 2.78, respectively.

The calculated grand mean of 2.97 indicates a generally low level of intragroup conflict among nurses. This finding is further supported by the homogeneity of responses, as evidenced by the standard deviation of 0.99. The presence of a small standard deviation suggests that the respondents' answers exhibit a high degree of similarity. This finding indicates that a significant proportion of the respondents are likely to be bedside nurses who may have limited exposure to intragroup conflict.

The findings of this study indicate that there was a low level of intragroup conflict observed among the nurses. The results can be attributed to the nurses who have accumulated considerable tenure within the institution, fostering and establishing reliable relationships with their colleagues in the unit. It is possible that these nurses are content with the quality of these relationships. This suggests that a sense of camaraderie and teamwork is evident at the unit level. In contrast, the researcher observed an incident where co-workers within the same unit actively avoided one another and refrained from engaging in workplace conversations. Consequently, it is possible that this incident represents an isolated occurrence.

As a result, individuals possess the ability to effectively navigate and address divergences and contradictions that may arise within a team or group, encompassing

disparities in resources, interests, values, beliefs, and work methodologies. The findings of the study also suggest that nurses who are part of a team can understand and effectively manage internal conflicts within the group to promote positive outcomes.

The findings were substantiated by a cross-sectional study conducted in Saudi Arabia, wherein it was observed that nurses exhibited a decreased sense of professionalism.

Notably, a statistically significant correlation was identified between intragroup conflict and this perception (Zakari et al., 2010 as cited in Dahshan & Moussa, 2019). This finding diverges from previous research conducted in Amman, Jordan, which indicated that nurses in the selected hospitals predominantly encountered a moderate level of conflict, specifically intragroup and competitive conflict, followed by disruptive conflict (Higazee, 2015).

This observation aligns with prior research in the field of conflict, which has consistently demonstrated the detrimental impact of relationship conflicts in the professional setting. A specific study focused on nurses determined that they encountered a moderate degree of conflict. According to the study conducted by Leon-Perez et al. (2016). Most probably respondents were found to have a high level of awareness about conflicts in their relationships involving group disagreements and incompatibilities within their department, as well as awareness of the group members' ideas and viewpoints about tasks and their performance, enabling them to develop approaches for mitigating intragroup conflicts to a low level.

Due to diversity in the workplace and misunderstanding among employees who work within the group, intra-group conflict develops (Evans, 2017). Conflicts in both

tasks and relationships arise as a result of individuals perceiving disparities in their interests and opinions regarding organizational practices. The development of emotional intelligence among team members will allow them to respond constructively in intragroup conflict situations, enabling them to regulate and express emotions in positively managing the conflict (Antunes et. al., 2012).

Table 6

*Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Conflict of the Respondents:
Intergroup Conflict*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
14	The employees that I see who are from other areas of the hospital are often difficult to deal with.	2.63	0.90
15	The various departments that I deal with in the hospital are usually helpful and make it easy to do my job.	3.75	0.66
16	Support services (Respiratory therapy, anesthesia techs,) are readily available when I need them.	3.74	0.77
Overall Mean		3.37	0.78

Perceived Conflict Scale Interpretation:

- 5 High Level
- 4 High Level
- 3 High Level
- 2 Low Level
- 1 Low Level

The level of perceived conflict among nurses in the dimension of intergroup conflict is presented in Table 6. In item 15, findings revealed a “high level” of intergroup conflict among nurses with departments in the hospital extending help for the ease of job performance, with the highest mean of 3.75 and support services being readily available when needed, perceived to be at “high level,” with a mean of 3.74. The nurses' perception of the level of difficulty in managing employees from other departments within the hospital is low, as indicated by a mean score of 2.63.

The calculated grand mean of 3.37 suggests a high level of intergroup conflict among nurses. This finding is further supported by the homogeneity of responses, as indicated by the standard deviation of 0.78. The small standard deviation indicates a small variation of subscale scores between nurses, which shows that nurses had the most similar responses; this implies that the majority of the staff have encountered intergroup conflict. This is possible because the hospital is a large institution with different departments, each of which has a different work culture and influences a more diverse group. Due to individuals not being accustomed to the way they behave or speak; it is misunderstood and causes intergroup conflict.

A study has been conducted to explore the significance of social identity and intergroup relationships in relation to power dynamics, control mechanisms, social status, and competitive behaviors. According to the study conducted by Hewett et al. in 2009, The observed phenomenon may potentially arise from interdepartmental hostility and breakdowns in communication during interpersonal exchanges. Poor communication with other departments has a significant impact on workflow, and nurses' respondents are not fully aware of the effects of intergroup conflict. With a high level of intergroup conflict in the workplace, nurse respondents were unable to foster

creativity, and the quality of their decisions will suffer, resulting in a deficiency in their intergroup conflict management skills. The nursing department and other services had a substantial effect on the given work-enabling support. Patient safety and workflow could be compromised by conflicts with other departments. Diversity in the workplace has been defined as having the potential for both positive and negative outcomes (Chrobot-Mason & Aramovich, 2013). But a low level of intergroup conflict at the hospital will indicate a high level of organizational performance since staff and supervisors will share the same opinions and collaborate in decision-making. Using the proper tools, intergroup conflicts in the healthcare workplace can be viewed as an opportunity for growth and beneficial outcomes (Ifeanyi & Babangid, 2020). A well-managed intergroup conflict enables the discussion of difficulties, with each party being encouraged to express their thoughts, resulting in the recognition of possible solutions that enhance organizational performance (Saaksvuori et al., 2011).

III. Level of Perceived Professionalism

Table 7

Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Professionalism of the Respondents: Outlook on Nursing as a Profession

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	The nurse must assume responsibility for diagnosing and treating human responses to actual or potential illness.	0.23	0.93
2	Nursing must be concerned equally with the prevention of disease and the conservation of health.	0.63	0.49
3	Nursing is an expression of one's commitment to others.	0.55	0.59
4	There is a right and wrong way to do things and to approach nursing situations.	0.49	0.70

5	The uniqueness of nursing lies in response to what nurses do in society, rather than in specific tasks they perform	0.41	0.77
6	There should be only one nursing theory.	0.18	0.96
7	Nurses should be free to practice nursing as they define it within the scope of professional autonomy.	0.60	0.62
8	Nurses should update their knowledge through lifelong continuing education.	0.47	0.52
9	Nurses must control and direct their practice.	0.60	0.58
10	Nurses must be aware that the people who require their assistance are helpless and dependent and usually need to be told what to do.	0.38	0.81
OVERALL MEAN		0.42	0.70

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale Interpretation:

+2	High Level
+1	High Level
0	High Level
-1	Low Level
-2	Low Level

Table 7 displays the data pertaining to the perceived professionalism of nurses within the hospital, specifically focusing on their outlook on nursing as a profession. In the second item, the results indicate that the respondents exhibit a notable degree of perception regarding disease prevention and health preservation, as evidenced by the highest mean score of 0.63. Items 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 exhibit a notable "high level" in relation to the following: The responsibilities of nurses encompass the diagnosis and treatment of human responses. Nursing is a manifestation of an individual's dedication to the well-being of others. It is important to approach nursing situations in a manner that adheres to established guidelines and best practices. The uniqueness of nursing lies in the responses generated by nurses within society. The ability to freely practice nursing is crucial, necessitating the continuous updating of knowledge and skills through ongoing education. Nurses should exercise control and

autonomy in directing their practice. It is noteworthy that there exists a singular nursing theory. Additionally, nurses must be cognizant of the fact that individuals requiring their assistance often find themselves in a state of helplessness and dependence. The mean values for the aforementioned variables are 0.23, 0.55, 0.49, 0.41, 0.60, 0.18, 0.47, 0.60, and 0.38, respectively.

The analysis of the data indicates that the grand mean for the dimension of outlook on nursing as a profession is 0.42. This value suggests a generally ‘high level’ of perceived professionalism among the nurse respondents. Furthermore, the homogeneity of responses is supported by the standard deviation of 0.70. This implies that the majority of nurses share similar perceptions and responses regarding their outlook on nursing as a profession.

The findings indicate that the nurse respondents have a comprehensive understanding of the essential professional standards and principles that govern their practice in the hospital. This understanding encompasses awareness of ethical standards, patient care norms, and regulatory mandates vital for delivering superior care.

Their thorough understanding of these standards demonstrates that they recognize their role expectations and appreciate the significance of compliance with these recommendations. This admiration for their nursing professions indicates an awareness of their influence on patient outcomes and the broader healthcare landscape. This also signifies a dedication to professional development and ongoing enhancement of their practice, which can elevate the quality of treatment provided in the hospital environment.

Based on the findings, the majority of the respondents have chosen this job as their profession because they do hold a strong opinion of nursing as a high-standard profession even if they encounter conflicts and challenges in the workplace, and nurses are resilient, overcoming struggles along their career path. In a study conducted by Cho and Kim (2014), it was found that there exists a significant positive correlation between nursing professionalism and nurse image. The researchers identified several factors that exerted an influence on nursing professionalism, including nurses' temperament, professionalism, career vision, role performance of nurses' images, and fundamental nursing practical experience.

In contrast to the findings of a cross-sectional study conducted by Godsey et al. (2020), which revealed a negative impact on factors influencing the inconsistent brand image of nursing, our research suggests that a range of education/credentials, image not being prioritized, lack of leadership development, lack of professionalism, portrayals in the media and online, patients' personal experiences, treatment by other professional colleagues, and gender role perceptions all contribute positively to the brand image of nursing. Nurses may also have experienced a restriction towards their nursing practice that withholds them in their decision-making and leads to disruption of work performance. However, their perceived level of professionalism towards nursing as a profession may be influenced by the expanded scope of their nursing career, which may be associated with an increased awareness of the importance of their work and contribution to patient care.

Respondents believe nurses are responsible for maintaining and updating the knowledge and skills necessary to provide nursing care, as well as being accountable to clients, the profession, employer, and society. To maintain accountability, nurses

must examine their practices and take action to protect nursing quality. Nurses have a perception on the adoption of a single theory, which may indicate that nurses believe the health care system must be continuously updated with evidence-based practice and utilize an appropriate nursing theory for patient care. This includes evaluating their commitment to their nursing job, identifying their own learning requirements, and pursuing ongoing education.

Moreover, personal and professional growth emphasizes portraying a professional image as a nurse, having a positive attitude toward change, and performing activities in accordance with professional standards. These refer to a person's capacity to manage his or her actions and appearance in social environments, and the nurse's actions should be based on sound, reasonable judgment and performed with confidence. Any hospital or organization should prioritize staff satisfaction with the advantages and rewards of their work, as well as respect and appreciation from employers, as these aspects influence nurses' perceptions of their profession, hence affecting nurse turnover and retention (Aljedaani, 2017). According to a study conducted by Al Yami and Watson (2014), the nursing profession is faced with challenges stemming from negative public perception and a perceived lack of professional recognition in the workplace. These factors have been found to contribute to a higher likelihood of nurses leaving the nursing profession.

Professional values in nursing include the maintenance of patients' confidentiality, meeting the health needs of a culturally diverse population, safeguarding the right to privacy of patients, and maintaining competency in nursing practice (Fisher, 2014). At the center of the promotion of the nursing profession is the

internalization and acquisition of values that become standards in guiding behavior and in nursing practice (Poorchangizi et al., 2019).

Table 8

Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Professionalism of the Respondents: Job Position of the Nurse

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
11	The independent functions of nurses include supervising the care of the clients/patients, observing and recording, supervising non-professional personnel, and health teaching.	0.63	0.55
12	Nurses must be involved actively in a professional organization.	0.58	0.50
13	Nurses should be responsible for conducting nursing care conferences routinely.	0.65	0.53
14	Nurses must assume responsibility for reviewing and evaluating the care provided by nursing peers.	0.59	0.62
15	Nurses must not hesitate to assume the role of the leader of the healthcare team when nurses best meet the client's/patient's problems.	0.66	0.55
16	Evaluation of the work of their peers and other nursing personnel should be the responsibility of nurses.	0.45	0.70
17	Nurses must take deliberate action to attain independence in a nursing situation.	0.69	0.49
18	Nurses should assume responsibility for the total nursing care of a caseload of clients/patients.	0.59	0.59
	OVERALL MEAN	0.60	0.57

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale Interpretation:

- +2 High Level
- +1 High Level
- 0 High Level
- 1 Low Level
- 2 Low Level

Table 8 displays the level of perceived professionalism within the job position of the nurse. In accordance with the results obtained in item 17, it has been observed that there exists a notable "high level" of perception among nurses regarding the necessity of actively pursuing independence in various nursing scenarios. This finding is supported by the highest mean value shown in this item, which represents 0.69.

The respondents in our study have demonstrated a notable level of perception regarding various aspects of nursing. Specifically, they have expressed a "high level" of agreement with the following statements: nurses should have independent functions, nurses should actively participate in professional organizations, nurses should be responsible for conducting nursing care conferences, nurses should review and evaluate the care provided by their peers, nurses should assume leadership roles within the healthcare team, nurses should evaluate the work of their peers and other nursing personnel, and nurses should take overall responsibility for the nursing care of their patients. These perceptions were measured using a Likert scale, and the mean values for these statements were found to be 0.63, 0.58, 0.65, 0.59, 0.66, 0.45, and 0.59, respectively.

The analysis of the data indicates that the grand mean, which is calculated to be 0.608, suggests a generally "high level" of perception among the respondents regarding perceived professionalism in the dimension of job position. This finding is further supported by the homogeneity of responses, as evidenced by the standard deviation of 0.57. Small standard deviation means small variation of scores between nurses; it implies a similar answer on their perception toward job position, which denotes that nurses in the hospital are fully aware of the work and their responsibilities

as nurses. It may also be related to the fact that most nurses are no longer novices and have already established their profession and expertise.

The hospital is currently experiencing a bed crisis and a staff shortage. It is obvious that reassignment of personnel and an increase in workload have impacted the daily duties and workload for nurses. However, based on the result, nurse respondents have a “high level” of perception toward their job position; this indicates that staff still have a positive view of their role as nurses and perceive their job as a calling and their autonomy and give importance to their position in the clinical setting. It is possible to conclude that the position or role is in high demand. According to Whetten and Cameron (2012), these components include the job title, description of duties, and agreement between the employee and the organization. The scope of their nursing job shows awareness of their roles in the hospital setting, which includes their role as a supervisor overlooking patient care and other staff members.

The nursing job position demonstrates skills and competencies for the effective performance of their job; thus, it is important to be part of a routine, up-to-date workshop and conferences and get involved in professional organizations and civic activities. “High Level” of perception on job position enabled them to achieve better performance of their role in the provision of support to a patient-centered approach to patient care, and awareness of their job position allows them to perform their role based on suitable attitudes and behaviors of professionalism in the nursing profession. Overall, the staff nurses demonstrated a very high regard for their responsibilities, as expected by the organization, which empowers them to improve job performance and their career.

Professionalism in job performance is linked to improved commitment, high quality patient outcomes, and job satisfaction of nurses; thus, the agreement of respondents that their job position allows them to maintain professionalism in the daily nursing practice achieves the required goals in care delivery (De Bragancaa & Nirmala, 2017).

Professionalism, attitudes, and behaviors of nurses shall be manifested in the performance of their nursing responsibilities through the job position, enabling them to achieve the goal of the provision of positive health outcomes for patients. The job position of nurses provides them with role clarity that increases their perceptions of professionalism and stability of job performance and increased psychological empowerment among nurses (Hossny et. al., 2020). With job positions, nurses perceive their roles to be well defined, are aware of the organization's expectations, and are therefore better equipped to provide high-quality care (Allemeh et. al., 2013; Mohamed & Hosny, 2020).

Table 9

Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Professionalism of the Respondents: Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
19	Nurses must be willing to enter with clients/patients those health-related situations which they cannot face alone.	0.63	0.59
20	Nursing is concerned with helping people maximize their health potential in their life situations.	0.69	0.50

21	Over action, directed by logical thought, toward meeting the client's patient's need for help constitutes the practice of clinical nursing.	0.58	0.58
22	Nurses should make written or verbal contracts with all appropriate persons to assure continuity of nursing care of clients/patients.	0.56	0.64
23	Nurses should be concerned primarily with giving physical care to clients/patients as directed by a doctor.	0.42	0.79
24	Nurses must follow doctor's orders without a question.	0.58	0.58
25	Nurses have responsibility for discussing the proposed medical plan of care with the doctor so that it can be adjusted, if possible, to be more acceptable to the client/patient.	0.63	0.53
OVERALL MEAN		0.38	0.63

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale Interpretation:

+2	High Level
+1	High Level
0	High Level
-1	Low Level
-2	Low Level

Table 9 presents the level of the perceived level of professionalism exhibited by nurses within the hospital setting, specifically in relation to their interactions with stakeholders. According to the findings in item 20, it is evident that the respondents possess a notable level of perception regarding the field of nursing. Specifically, their perception revolves around the notion of assisting individuals in optimizing their health potential within the context of their unique life circumstances. This perception is characterized by a remarkably high mean score of 0.69, indicating the prominence of this aspect among the respondents' perceptions.

The analysis of the data reveals that among the nurse respondents, a "high level" is observed on items 19, 21, 22, 23, 24, and 25. Nurses are required to demonstrate a willingness to accompany clients or patients in health-related scenarios

where they are unable to confront the challenges independently. The practice of clinical nursing involves the application of logical thought and deliberate actions aimed at addressing the needs of clients or patients in a proactive manner. It is recommended that nurses establish written or verbal agreements with all relevant parties to ensure the consistent provision of nursing care. Additionally, nurses should adhere to the physician's instructions regarding the physical care provided to patients. Nurses are entrusted with the important task of engaging in discussions with physicians regarding the proposed medical plan of care. This collaborative effort aims to potentially modify the plan to better align with the preferences and needs of the client or patient. It is expected that nurses adhere to the instructions provided by the physician without hesitation. The mean values associated with the aforementioned data points are 0.63, 0.58, 0.56, 0.42, 0.58, and 0.63.

The grand mean of 0.38 shows the overall “high level” perception of the respondent nurses on their perceived professionalism in the dimension of their relationships with stakeholders, supported by a standard deviation of 0.63. The observed small standard deviation suggests that there is minimal variation in the responses provided by nurses regarding their perception of the nurse-client relationship, as well as their interactions with doctors and other health allied members. This finding indicates a high level of consensus among the respondents, suggesting that a majority of nurses possess a strong awareness of the importance of maintaining professionalism in their interactions with others.

The tertiary hospital implements the highest international standard of care with a large population of patients throughout the kingdom; thus, the findings demonstrated that respondents are fully aware of the critical relationships they must maintain in order

to be competent in the creation of a therapeutic relationship framework in the nursing profession and probably were mindful of the expectations placed on them in terms of creating and maintaining proper professional boundaries within therapeutic relationships with clients.

Since the nurse respondents have been employed by the institution for a longer period, they are aware that helping people and emphasizing health are the most important goals. They also believe that patients depend on the nurses for their care and management, requiring effective clinical practice and quality care, and they are aware that nurses are responsible for communicating with doctors about the patient's condition and the best possible care plan. It also highlights how important documentation and the proper referral procedure are to a patient's progress. Nurses have a high level of perception of obeying medical orders, indicating that nurses desire autonomy. Extremely hierarchic and strict administrative structure, along with regulatory law of nursing practice, may be responsible for insufficient autonomy among nurses (Shanaz et al., 2020). Nurse respondents may encounter challenges in upholding a consistent level of professionalism within the workplace, particularly when interacting with other stakeholders. These difficulties can be attributed to factors such as excessive workloads and a stressful environment. The consequences of compromised professionalism are not limited to the individual nurse but also extend to the institution and the quality of services delivered. It is important to note that the quality of patient care is heavily reliant on the performance and conduct of both nurses and physicians (Terzioglu, Temel, & Uslu, 2016). To effectively address the requirements of the client, it is imperative to carefully evaluate their needs, priorities, and preferences.

Additionally, one must consider the available resources and services that can be utilized to meet these needs. Furthermore, fostering a sense of shared accountability and promoting mutual respect between all parties involved is crucial for successful outcomes. To effectively provide care that addresses the therapeutic needs of patients, it is imperative for nurses to establish a relationship that is both goal-directed and planned with clients and healthcare professionals (Canadian Nurses Association, 2019).

Nurses cultivate and maintain professional relationships while establishing appropriate boundaries within the healthcare environment, with the goal of delivering high-quality care services (Canadian Nurses Association, 2017). By setting and preserving these boundaries, nurses effectively address the care needs of their clients within the healthcare setting.

IV. Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Level of Conflict and Perceived Level of Professionalism

Table 10

Distribution of nurses according to Perceived Level of Conflict and Perceived Level of Professionalism.

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (by subscale)	Interpersonal Conflict		Intrapersonal Conflict		Intragroup Conflict		Intergroup Conflict	
	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
Outlook on nursing as a profession	0.154	<.001	0.160	<.001	0.065	0.154	0.146	0.001
Job Position of the Nurse	0.073	0.109	0.054	0.236	0.006	0.898	0.136	0.003
Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.	0.039	0.393	0.068	0.135	0.039	0.398	0.054	0.236

**p-values less than .05 are considered significant.*

The correlation analysis is presented in Table 10, which displays the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) along with its associated p-value for each combination of variables. At a significance level of 5%, Based on the analysis conducted, it has been determined that the null hypothesis is rejected. Based on the available evidence, it can be determined that there exists a notable correlation between the level of professionalism in the Outlook on Nursing as a Profession and the various subscales of conflict, namely interpersonal conflict, intrapersonal conflict, and intergroup conflict. Pearson's r correlations for interpersonal conflict ($r = 0.154$), intrapersonal conflict ($r = 0.160$), and intergroup conflict ($r = 0.146$) show a weak uphill (positive) linear relationship with the nurses' outlook on nursing as a profession. An increase in the aforementioned conflict subscales is correlated with an increase in the level of professional outlook. Surprisingly, conflict was positively related to professionalism, meaning that nurses who were encountering conflict had a high level of professionalism. The findings suggest that nurse respondents may encounter various forms of conflict, including interpersonal, intrapersonal, and intergroup conflict. Notably, the level of perceived professionalism in nursing appears to be positively associated with the severity of these conflicts. Consequently, any alterations in the dynamics of interpersonal, intrapersonal, and intergroup conflict are likely to impact the overall perception of nursing as a profession among nurses within the organization.

The findings of this study indicate the presence of interpersonal, intrapersonal, and intergroup conflict within the hospital setting. This can be attributed to the hospital's multinational composition and its highly dynamic nature. Consequently, the provision of care services is based on collaborative relationships that lead to organizational conflict.

To resolve conflicts among nurses, nurses must use effective communication and interpersonal skills, particularly during interactions with other healthcare professionals. To prevent interpersonal, intragroup, or intergroup conflict, nurses must detect and address concerns as soon as they arise. This allows nurses to maintain professionalism in nursing practice by identifying the most appropriate conflict resolution approach, and this enables nurses to preserve their professionalism in nursing practice by determining the method of conflict resolution that is most appropriate for the given situation. In the realm of medical practice, conflict is unavoidable, and frequently, nurses find themselves in the center of the conflict (Simpao, 2013). Professionalism in nursing practice provides the ability of nurses to handle conflict with confidence, arousing the best results in conflict management (Allied Academies International Conference, 2010). Conflict is a normal aspect of work life, and constructive conflict with favorable resolution can create solutions to problems, provide independence in decision-making, and foster relationships (Arafat et al., 2018). Utilizing nursing professionalism, conflict can be managed positively, contributing to growth and positive change in the organization. Therefore, conflict resolution is accomplished best (Chang et. al., 2017). The level of conflict and the workplace environment influence nurses' ability to practice professionalism in nursing (Al-Hamdan et al., 2014).

A statistically significant association exists between the intergroup conflict subscale and the job position of nurses, with a level of significance set at 5%. Pearson's r correlation for intergroup conflict ($r = 0.136$) shows a weak uphill (positive) linear relationship with the nurses' role, either as bedside nurses or in managerial posts. Therefore, there is a correlation between an increase in intergroup conflict and an increase in job professionalism. This could demonstrate that a change in the

perceived level of intergroup conflict will lead to a change in the perceived level of professionalism among nurses in the organization. This result suggests that a higher level of conflict is related to nurses' ability to maintain a higher level of professionalism. The findings demonstrate the influence of both the working environment and the high level of intergroup conflict that exists among nurses working in healthcare settings, as well as the nurses' ability to maintain a professional level of nursing practice.

This study corresponds to the results reported by Zakari et al. (2010), as cited by Dahshan and Moussa (2019), which found a statistically significant correlation between intergroup conflict and perceptions of professionalism among nurses. However, other research has indicated lower levels of perceptions of professionalism, potentially influenced by factors such as nurses' experiences, devotion to the nursing profession, family, clients, and societal perspectives on professionalism (El-Hosany, 2017). The other variable pairings are shown to have no significant relationships at a 5% level of significance. The lack of a substantial correlation between interpersonal, intrapersonal, intergroup, and intragroup conflict and the nurse's relationship with patients, doctors, and other healthcare professionals may be explained by the levels of conflict among nurses within the hospital organization.

However, when there is a high level of conflict, it suggests that nurses are skilled at preventing instances of disagreement, opposition, and incompatibility between different groups and teams within the organization. The nurses' perceived level of professionalism in their relationships with co-workers, patients, doctors, or other health-related members is not influenced by conflicts. Findings revealed that nurses do not experience tension, incompatibility, negative emotional reactions, or inconsistency in their interests despite being interdependent and the existence of a

variety of situational backgrounds and conditions, thereby not influencing their level of professionalism.

As parties experience disagreements and negative emotional reactions that interfere with the achievement of their goals, the phenomenon of conflict arises, occurring more likely with the existence of a variety of dispositional conditions (Almost, 2010). Intrapersonal and intragroup conflicts can have indirect effects on the productivity of individuals and the whole organization (Saridi et al., 2019).

V. Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Level of Conflict and

Sociodemographic Profile of the Respondents:

Table 11

Distribution of nurses according to sociodemographic profile and perceived level of Conflict

Perceived Conflict Scale (by subscale)	Chi-square Coefficient			
	Age	Years of Experience	Nationality	Gender
Interpersonal Conflict	24.56 (0.544)	50.75 (0.523)	123.29 (0.014)	5.84 (0.952)
Intrapersonal Conflict	51.92 (0.042)	72.75 (0.453)	588.27 (<0.001)	34.33 (0.011)
Intragroup Conflict	27.47 (0.493)	72.26 (0.071)	82.95 (0.862)	7.52 (0.913)
Intergroup Conflict	20.00 (0.333)	28.29 (0.817)	85.50 (0.031)	7.86 (0.548)

**p-values less than .05 are considered significant*

Table 11 presents the use of Chi-square tests in order to ascertain the presence of a statistically significant association between the two variables, with a level of

significance set at 5%. The null hypothesis is rejected due to sufficient evidence suggesting a significant relationship between the age of nurses and the level of intrapersonal conflict they experience.

The findings indicate that the nurses' age group has a significant effect on the increase or decrease of their intrapersonal conflict scores. As a result, intrapersonal conflict scores may differ among age groups. As nurses become older, they gain the abilities needed for conflict resolution and can determine the best resolution methods for keeping organizational disputes to a minimum. Nurses' conflict resolution strategies can also be influenced by their age, with younger nurses adopting solutions with fewer responsibilities or avoidance strategies when they lack enough knowledge of conflict management.

When nurses were categorized by age, Lahana et al. (2017) found that there was a significant variation in the conflict-resolution techniques they employed. Younger nurses may employ an avoidance strategy to resolve disputes because they are worried about the repercussions or lack the necessary expertise (Iglesias et al., 2012). Age-related conflicts become less frequent when people gain experience and maturity at work, due to the respect that is shown to them (Akpabio et al., 2015).

The findings indicate a significant relationship between nurses' nationality and their scores for interpersonal conflict, intrapersonal conflict, and intergroup conflict, suggesting that nationality plays a crucial role in shaping how nurses experience and perceive conflict in the workplace. Specifically, the data reveal that the level of conflict experienced by nurses varies significantly across different nationalities, implying that cultural backgrounds can influence interpersonal dynamics and conflict resolution strategies. Additionally, it was noted that nurses from different countries do not receive

the same level of education, which affects their development of essential skills and competencies in nursing. This variation in educational background can lead to differences in proficiency within the work environment, contributing to diverse experiences of conflict.

Cultural diversities may further impact nurses' perceptions of conflict, as different cultural norms and practices shape how conflicts are interpreted and managed. This highlights the need for tailored conflict resolution approaches in a multicultural nursing workforce. The results also emphasize that the education provided by tertiary institutions globally aims to foster critical thinking and independent nursing roles, enhancing nurses' confidence in delivering exceptional care (Lasebikan et al., 2012). However, disparities in educational quality can lead to differing levels of preparedness among nurses. Furthermore, the influence of work-related conflicts on job performance is moderated by professional qualifications, with nurses holding graduate degrees reportedly being less affected by workplace conflicts. This indicates that higher education equips them with better coping mechanisms and skills to handle challenges in their roles (Akpabio et al., 2015).

Overall, these findings highlight the complex interplay between nationality, education, and conflict in the nursing profession, suggesting that addressing these disparities may be essential for improving workplace harmony and enhancing the overall quality of care provided by nurses.

Furthermore, based on a significance level of 5%, there is substantial evidence to support the hypothesis that there exists a significant association between the gender and their intrapersonal conflict scores. This observation suggests that there is a notable impact of gender on the changes in individuals' scores pertaining to

intrapersonal conflict. The scores of the male nurses are different (may be higher or lower) than the scores of the female nurses for intrapersonal conflict. The results suggest that there are differences in the perceptions of conflict levels between male and female nurses. The results indicate that there are variations in the perceptions of strategy selection for conflict resolution and the level of conflict within the organization between males and females. Gender-related social factors affecting nurse behaviors in the delivery of clinical services were found to affect the maintenance of the perceived level of conflict among nurses. Respondent nurses were found to have various ways of perceiving information, which can lead to organizational conflicts.

There can be a statistically significant difference in the utilization of strategies for conflict resolution based on the gender of nursing personnel (Al-Hamali et al., 2013). Nurse supervisors must consider how gender may affect nurse conflict. Perceptions in the workplace can be related to styles of problem-solving, organizational structure, several work styles, or views of work-related conflict (Akpabio et al., 2015).

At a significance level of 5%, there is no significant relationship between the duration of professional experience and the perceived level of conflict experienced by nurses employed within the hospital setting. The results suggest that there are no significant changes in perceptions of conflict levels among nurses with different years of experience.

Findings show that regardless of the number of years of experience, nurses develop conflict resolution strategies similarly, and there is no significant relationship in the adoption of conflict resolution strategies in the organization. Nurses can maintain

conflict at the lowest level and are found to agree on issues for the resolution of organizational conflicts.

In the early stages of the nursing career, nurses may encounter interpersonal conflicts that can result in a significant level of missing work. Consequently, it becomes imperative to provide training to nurses in effectively managing and resolving conflicts (Higazee, 2015). With more years of experience on the job, nurses move higher on the professional ranks ladder, allowing them to develop skills essential for coping with work-related conflict situations (Akpabio et al., 2015). When accompanied by higher levels of education, years of experience enable nurses to advance in professional ranks that develop the required competencies in the management of work-related conflicts (Al-Hamali et al., 2013).

VI. Significant Relationship Between Perceived Level of Professionalism and the Sociodemographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 12

Distribution of nurses according to sociodemographic profile and perceived level of professionalism

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (by subscale)	Chi-square Coefficient			
	Age	Years of Experience	Nationality	Gender
Outlook on nursing as a profession	38.60 (0.442)	84.74 (0.231)	196.20 (<0.001)	21.56 (0.307)
Job Position of the Nurse	27.11 (0.404)	53.21 (0.427)	247.36 (<0.001)	16.13 (0.242)
Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.	13.46 (0.958)	52.73 (0.296)	67.38 (0.908)	8.31 (0.761)

**p-values less than .05 are considered significant.*

Table 12 shows using Chi-square tests to determine whether there is a significant association between the two variables at a 5% level of significance (per profile). The null hypothesis was rejected based on compelling evidence that reveals a significant association between nurses' nationality and their perspectives on nursing as a profession, as well as their job positions within the nursing field. This suggests that a majority of the respondents are expatriates from various countries, each bringing unique cultural identities and ethnic backgrounds that may influence their outlook on nursing and their job position scores. Notably, some nationalities exhibit a higher degree of professionalism in these areas compared to others.

The findings indicate that professionalism among nurse respondents has been cultivated through their job positions, reflecting attitudes, knowledge, and behaviors grounded in essential nursing principles and standards. This professionalism manifests in the delivery of safe and high-quality healthcare services, underscoring the importance of knowledge and behaviors based on regulations and nursing standards, which are critical for successful clinical practice (Tanaka et al., 2014, cited by Bekalu & Wudu, 2023).

Moreover, the skills developed through nurses' job positions enable them to provide comprehensive care, ensuring safe, competent, and ethical care across all healthcare settings (Suresh, 2013). Professionalism mandates that nurses critically analyze their roles, guiding their behaviors in practice to uphold care quality at the highest level (Alidina, 2013).

Importantly, the data suggest that nationality significantly relates to the perceived level of professionalism. This implies that a nurse's nationality influences their capacity to utilize their competencies in nursing professionalism for the delivery

of safe and ethical care, as well as high-quality clinical services. Respondents from diverse national backgrounds provide varying levels of comprehensive and therapeutic care, highlighting the scientific foundations underlying nursing professionalism.

Nursing professionalism encompasses several key attributes, including knowledge, accountability, innovation, collaboration, a spirit of inquiry, autonomy, and ethics (De Braganca & Nirmala, 2017). Effective communication of professionalism to the public is essential for the growth and success of the nursing profession (Skela-Savic, 2016).

In summary, these data highlight the intricate relationship between nationality and professionalism in nursing. Creating a supportive atmosphere for varied nursing practitioners can improve the overall quality of care and fortify the nursing profession. Recognizing the distinct cultural and educational backgrounds of nurses is essential for enhancing their contributions to healthcare and improving patient outcomes.

Meanwhile, at a 5% level of significance, all other variable pairings have no significant relationships with each other. There is no significant relationship between age and the perceived level of professionalism among nurses. A change in age will not significantly result in changes in the perceived level of professionalism.

The finding implies that a change in the age of the nurse respondents will not influence their perceived level of professionalism. Younger respondents can abide by the principles and standards of nursing professionalism in their medical and clinical practice.

There is no significant relationship between gender and perceived professionalism in this study. Therefore, male and female nurses do not vary

significantly in this regard. The inequality of the sample size in each sociodemographic variable may affect the absence of significant results. Based on the findings, it is possible to contemplate that the majority of the respondents are equipped with knowledge, skills, competencies, and certification into the nursing profession, regardless of gender, allowing them to practice behavioral norms of professionalism with their attitudes that represent work commitment. Males and females have developed the set of behaviors and attitudes appropriate to the nursing profession, relative to clients and society. Regardless of gender, the respondents demonstrate professionalism, which is evident in their professional approach that aligns with the essential standards, regulations, and principles of successful nursing practice. Dikmen et al. (2016) argue that there exists a potential correlation between the gender of nurses and the manifestation of an increased degree of professionalism.

There is no significant correlation between the number of years of experience and the perceived level of professionalism. The finding implies that a change in the number of years of experience of nurses does not create a significant difference in the nurses' level of perceived professionalism. Even novice nurses are expected to have developed the required level of skills and competencies to deliver clinical services at the highest standards of professionalism. Findings show that professionalism in nursing practice is expected to be maintained by all nurses at the highest level, regardless of the number of years of service they have rendered in the organization.

As nursing practice promotes positive health outcomes and client satisfaction, there is a need for nurses, regardless of their years of experience, to demonstrate professionalism in their routine medical practice (Al-Sudani et al., 2013). Professionalism at higher levels improves nursing practice quality, promotes job

satisfaction among nurses, improves autonomy and empowerment, and facilitates organizational citizenship behaviors (De Braganca & Nirmala, 2017).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the research findings and conclusions pertaining to the perceived level of conflict and professionalism among nurses in a tertiary hospital located in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The concluding section of the Chapter presents a recommendation for future research endeavors pertaining to the topic of Conflict and Professionalism among Nurses.

Summary of Findings

The aim of this study was to investigate the correlation between conflict and professionalism among nurses employed in a tertiary hospital in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study determined the socio-demographic profile of the nurses and examined their perceived level of conflict and perceived level of professionalism. In addition, it also determines if there is an association of sociodemographic profile (age, years of experience, nationality, and gender) on nurses' perceived level of conflict and perceived level of professionalism.

The majority of participants fall within the age bracket of 30 to 39 years old, accounting for 53.4% of the sample. These individuals can be classified as adults. Most of the respondents have worked in the hospital for 5 to 9 years (31.3%), followed by those who have 10 to 14 (23.6%) years of experience and with 2 to 4 (23%) years of experience, and the smallest respondents have 15 (11.8%) years or more working in the hospital. Most of the respondents come from the Philippines (67.9%), followed by the second-biggest group of respondents from India (21.9%), then from Saudi

Arabia (5.4%), ranked third. The small groups are from Jordan (1.9%), Pakistan (0.8%), South Africa (1.2%), and Malaysia (0.6%), and the smallest group is from Palestine (0.2%). Most of the respondents were female (81.6%) outnumbered by male (18.4%) respondents.

The descriptive analysis indicates that nurses in the tertiary hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, perceived a high level of conflict. This is evident by the high scores in each of the tested subscales of the Perceived Conflict Scale: interpersonal conflict ($M = 3.23$, $SD = 1.00$), intrapersonal conflict ($M = 3.04$, $SD = 1.03$), and intergroup conflict ($M = 3.37$, $SD = 0.78$). However, a low-level show on the intragroup conflict ($M = 2.9$, $SD = 0.99$).

Likewise, there is a perceived high level of professionalism among staff nurses, that is based on the high scores they rated: Outlook on Nursing as a Profession ($M = 0.422$, $SD = 0.700$), Job Position of the Nurses ($M = 0.608$, $SD = 0.572$), and Relationship of the Nurse to the Client/Patient and the Physician and other health team members ($M = 0.381$, $SD = 0.636$).

In this study, it was revealed that level of conflict on the subscale of interpersonal, intrapersonal, and intergroup has a statistically significant correlation with the perception of professionalism on the subscale of outlook on nursing as a profession ($p < 0.05$), and it also shows a significant relationship between intergroup conflict and job position ($p < 0.05$). However, there is evidence to conclude that there is no statistically significant relationship between overall conflict (interpersonal, intrapersonal, intergroup, intragroup) and the relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health-allied members ($p > 0.05$).

The findings of the study revealed that there was no statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of nurses, specifically their years of experience, and their perceived level of conflict ($p > 0.05$). At the same time, the sociodemographic profile such as age, years of experience, and gender showed no significant relationship among nurses in terms of their perceived level of professionalism ($p > 0.05$).

Nevertheless, the study results indicated that nationality is positively associated with conflict and professionalism among nurses.

Conclusion

The hospital operates within a complex network of relationships, rivalries, and interdependencies across its various departments. This study reveals a significant correlation between nurses' perceived levels of conflict and their professionalism, which can directly affect their work performance and interactions with colleagues and patients. As a result, these dynamics have the potential to influence the quality of patient care and, in turn, compromise patient safety.

The process of self-assessment regarding one's perceptions of conflict and professionalism provides nurses with a valuable opportunity to introspect and evaluate their ability to effectively manage conflicts while upholding professional standards. In light of these research findings, the importance of understanding the concepts of conflict and professionalism is validated. This underscores the role of staff nurses and nursing management in recognizing how enhancing professionalism can effectively

reduce conflicts and proactively address issues before they escalate into more complicated situations.

Consequently, hospital management plays a crucial role in prioritizing staff and leadership development programs, organizational training, and building frameworks that promote proactive conflict management strategies. Such strategies can improve the professional well-being of nurses, enhance the hospital work environment, and ultimately lead to improved patient safety. Additionally, it is essential to establish a clear scope of practice for nurses to preserve professionalism in the workplace. Providing professional support by strengthening role identification through clear benefits, rewards, and promotional pathways is also crucial, as this can serve as an effective strategy to enhance professionalism and commitment to the profession.

The study identifies a significant correlation between gender and conflict, suggesting that gender influences conflict through differences in behavior, communication styles, and conflict resolution strategies. Men may adopt more assertive approaches, while women tend to prioritize collaboration and relationship-building. These findings highlight the importance of considering gender dynamics when addressing workplace conflict to promote effective resolution and enhance team cohesion.

The research findings indicate that as nurses age, they develop cognitive and emotional skills that enhance their ability to manage workplace conflicts. With experience, they become more adept at recognizing and applying effective conflict resolution strategies, leading to improved conflict management.

The present study also show a clear correlation between an individual's nationality and their perceived levels of professionalism and conflict. As cultural

differences affect communication patterns, conflict resolution techniques, and expectations regarding teamwork and hierarchy, nationality seems to influence how nurses see and experience conflict in the workplace. Nurses from cultures that give direct communication, for example, may freely address conflicts; those from cultures that value harmony may avoid confrontation. This implies that nationality greatly influences the experience and handling of differences that arise inside nursing teams.

Additionally, the research reveals that nationality impacts perceived levels of professionalism. Professionalism in nursing, which includes behaviors such as accountability, ethical decision-making, collaboration, and adherence to standards, is influenced by the cultural and educational contexts in which nurses are trained. These variations suggest that nationality shapes how nurses understand and apply professional principles in clinical practice.

In conclusion, these findings highlight the significant relationship between nationality and both conflict perception and professionalism among nurses. This emphasizes the need for healthcare organizations to consider the cultural diversity of their workforce when implementing conflict resolution strategies and fostering professionalism. Tailoring training programs to address the unique cultural backgrounds of nurses can help reduce workplace conflict and promote a unified standard of professionalism, ultimately enhancing the quality of care provided in diverse healthcare settings.

The overall results suggest that socio-demographic attributes such as gender, age, and nationality, along with cultural backgrounds and beliefs, are influential factors that significantly affect perceptions of conflict and conflict management while maintaining professionalism. This study has yielded valuable insights into enhancing

organizational comprehension of different generations, diverse backgrounds, and genders, thereby promoting gender and cultural sensitivity as well as mutual respect in the fulfillment of nursing professional duties.

Recommendations

To Staff Nurses

The researcher recommends that staff nurses, particularly bedside nurses, actively engage in training aimed at increasing awareness and understanding of their working environment. Attending lectures on topics such as conflict management and resolution strategies will help them identify potential conflict situations and develop effective solutions. This training will empower nurses to express their thoughts candidly while maintaining professionalism.

Additionally, it can foster better working relationships among peers in the healthcare field and promote effective communication within multicultural teams, enhancing collaboration with coworkers and other healthcare professionals.

The researcher also recommends strengthening the utilization of the hospital's grievance committee and the existing opportunity reporting system, which addresses various behavioral issues.

To hospital and nursing service administrators

The researcher recommends that strong management support is essential for fostering a conflict-free environment in the hospital, emphasizing the importance of addressing conflicts and promoting professionalism. This research paper aims to

provide nursing directors and nurse managers with valuable insights into the relationship between conflict and professionalism.

Programs such as “Crucial Conversations” should be implemented to enhance self-awareness regarding individual thoughts and feelings. Encouraging introspection through targeted activities will lead to a deeper understanding of oneself and others, which is beneficial for conflict resolution and maintaining professionalism.

Furthermore, leaders, particularly new head nurses or unit managers, should attend workshops focused on self-awareness, conflict resolution, coaching, and crisis management to build their confidence and preparedness in handling workplace conflicts.

Nurse leaders must enhance their leadership and management skills to cultivate a healthy workplace culture and a conflict-free environment, ultimately motivating nurses to perform more efficiently. Policymakers should also review existing policies and operational guidelines to emphasize the improvement of professionalism and conflict management.

To Nursing Educators

The nursing educators should provide support to nurses by imparting knowledge and promoting the utilization of the opportunity reporting system. Additionally, it is recommended that the educators reiterate the importance of this system during the general nursing orientation.

It is recommended to establish an awareness program and provide training services focused on conflict resolution, crisis management, effective communication skills, and the appropriate escalation process for reporting in line with policy. Tailoring

these training programs to address the diverse cultural backgrounds of nurses can help minimize workplace conflict and foster a unified standard of professionalism, ultimately improving the quality of care in varied healthcare environments.

To promote the advancement of knowledge in the nursing profession, it is essential to encourage nurses to pursue graduate degrees, which are vital for equipping them with the skills and competencies necessary to perform their nursing duties and roles. As a result, this education will enable them to deliver high-quality care and progress into management and leadership positions.

To Patients

The researcher recommends a study on patient satisfaction to identify factors that may affect the degree of professionalism of nurses. This will improve healthcare management and patient services.

To recognize that the tertiary hospital is a multi-cultural setting; consequently, it is essential to enhance cultural sensitivity in the hospital context to avoid conflict and maintain professionalism. Participate in all conflict prevention activities that will help society.

To Researchers

This study examines the significant aspects of nurses' perspectives on conflict and professionalism, which will facilitate a more professional approach to conflict resolution and serve as a reminder that nurses' behaviors and attitudes toward colleagues, other departments, and patients must be taken into consideration. This study can be disseminated to raise awareness and increase nurses' understanding of

hospital-based conflict, especially here in the Arab country, and showcase its relevance to professionalism. This is important to provide the highest quality care and ensure patient safety.

To Future Researcher

The researcher suggests future study by determining the relationship of conflict and professionalism in a qualitative approach to obtain a better understanding of the hospital's conflict-free culture and the application of professionalism.

In conclusion, a larger-scale study is suggested to determine if the outcome of this study can be generalized.

Further study be undertaken, with a focus on qualitative methods, to understand and validate the perceived conflict and professionalism among staff nurses. To strengthen the generalizability of findings about nurses' experience of conflict in hospitals and other health care institutions, other researchers are strongly encouraged to replicate this study in different geographic regions. Develop future interventions and programs to minimize workplace conflict and preserve professionalism through the development of evidence-based practice.

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Appendices

Appendix A
Dummy Tables

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage distribution of sociodemographic profile (n=483)

Variable	Category	Frequency	(Percentage %)
Age (years)	Less than 30	X	X
	30-39	X	X
	40+	X	X
Years of Experience as Registered Nurse in KFMC	Above 6 months – 1 year	X	X
	2 – 4 years	X	X
	5 – 9 years	X	X
	10 – 14 years	X	X
	15 years & above	X	X
Nationality	Philippines	X	X
	India	X	X
	Saudi Arabia	X	X
	Jordan	X	X
	Pakistan	X	X
	South Africa	X	X
	Malaysia	X	X
	Palestine	X	X
Gender	Male	X	X
	Female	X	X

Table 2 Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Conflict of the Respondents

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
Interpersonal Conflict		X	X
1	Another nurse often disagrees with each other about how work in this unit should be handled.	X	X
2	My supervisor and I usually agree with what my job is, and the requirements I must fulfil.	X	X
3	Patients often demand that I do things that I just cannot do.	X	X
4	When I do something that satisfies one person or group, other people are frequently upset with what I have done.	X	X
Overall Mean		X	X
Intrapersonal Conflict			
5	My obligations to my work frequently conflict with my obligations to my family, friends, or myself (outside the job).	X	X
6	I often cannot get equipment, supplies, or medications when I need them.	X	X
7	I often have too many things to do at one time.	X	X
8	I usually agree with the decisions my supervisor makes.	X	X
9	My patients often make requests or need care that I feel I should provide but cannot because I lack the time or energy.	X	X
Overall Mean		X	X
Intragroup Conflict		X	X
10	I frequently encounter problems when I transfer my patients to other units or departments.	X	X
11	I usually agree with the way other nurses think things should be done on this unit.	X	X
12	Many times, the things that support services are supposed to do are not adequately done, and I either must argue with another unit, or do someone else's job.	X	X

13	I am unable to provide adequate patient care because of the time that I spend dealing with hospital rules.	X	X
Overall Mean		X	X
Intergroup Conflict		X	X
14	The employees that I see who are from other areas of the hospital are often difficult to deal with.	X	X
15	The various departments that I deal with in the hospital are usually helpful and make it easy to do my job.	X	X
16	Support services (Respiratory therapy, anesthesia techs,) are readily available when I need them.	X	X
Overall Mean		X	X

Table 3 Means and Standard Deviation of Perceived Level of Professionalism of the Respondents

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
Outlook on Nursing as a Profession			
1	The nurse must assume responsibility for diagnosing and treating human responses to actual or potential illness.	X	X
2	Nursing must be concerned equally with the prevention of disease and the conservation of health.	X	X
3	Nursing is an expression of one's commitment to others.	X	X
4	There is a right and wrong way to do things and to approach nursing situations.	X	X
5	The uniqueness of nursing lies in response to what nurses do in society, rather than in specific tasks they perform	X	X
6	There should be only one nursing theory.	X	X
7	Nurses should be free to practice nursing as they define it within the scope of professional autonomy.	X	X

8	Nurses should update their knowledge through lifelong continuing education.	X	X
9	Nurses must control and direct their practice.	X	X
10	Nurses must be aware that the people who require their assistance are helpless and dependent and usually need to be told what to do.	X	X
OVERALL MEAN		X	X
Job Position of the Nurse			
11	The independent functions of nurses include supervising the care of the clients/patients, observing and recording, supervising non-professional personnel, and health teaching.	X	X
12	Nurses must be involved actively in a professional organization.	X	X
13	Nurses should be responsible for conducting nursing care conferences routinely.	X	X
14	Nurses must assume responsibility for reviewing and evaluating the care provided by nursing peers.	X	X
15	Nurses must not hesitate to assume the role of the leader of the healthcare team when nurses best meet the client's/patient's problems.	X	X
16	Evaluation of the work of their peers and other nursing personnel should be the responsibility of nurses.	X	X
17	Nurses must take deliberate action to attain independence in a nursing situation.	X	X
18	Nurses should assume responsibility for the total nursing care of a caseload of clients/patients.	X	X
OVERALL MEAN		X	X
Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.			
19	Nurses must be willing to enter with clients/patients those health-related situations which they cannot face alone.	X	X

20	Nursing is concerned with helping people maximize their health potential in their life situations.	X	X
21	Over action, directed by logical thought, toward meeting the client's patient's need for help constitutes the practice of clinical nursing.	X	X
22	Nurses should make written or verbal contracts with all appropriate persons to assure continuity of nursing care of clients/patients.	X	X
23	Nurses should be concerned primarily with giving physical care to clients/patients as directed by a doctor.	X	X
24	Nurses must follow doctor's orders without a question.	X	X
25	Nurses have responsibility for discussing the proposed medical plan of care with the doctor so that it can be adjusted, if possible, to be more acceptable to the client/patient.	X	X
OVERALL MEAN		X	X

Table 4 Distribution of nurses according to Perceived Level of Conflict and Perceived Level of Professionalism

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (by subscale)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient							
	Interpersonal Conflict		Intrapersonal Conflict		Intragroup Conflict		Intergroup Conflict	
	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
Outlook on nursing as a profession	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Job Position of the Nurse	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Relationship of the nurse to the client,	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

doctors, and other health allied members.								
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Table 5 Distribution of nurses according to sociodemographic profile and perceived level of Conflict

Perceived Conflict Scale (by subscale)	Chi-square Coefficient			
	Age	Years of Experience	Nationality	Gender
Interpersonal Conflict	X	X	X	X
Intrapersonal Conflict	X	X	X	X
Intragroup Conflict	X	X	X	X
Intergroup Conflict	X	X	X	X

Table 6 Distribution of nurses according to sociodemographic profile and perceived level of professionalism

Valiga Concept of Nursing Scale (by subscale)	Chi-square Coefficient			
	Age	Years of Experience	Nationality	Gender
Outlook on nursing as a profession	X	X	X	X
Job Position of the Nurse	X	X	X	X
Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.	X	X	X	X

APPENDIX B

INSTITUTION REVIEW BOARD (IRB) APPROVAL

التجمع الصحي الثاني بالمنطقة الوسطى
Central Second Health Cluster

IRB Registration Number with KACST, KSA: H-01-R-012
IRB Registration Number with OHRP/NIH, USA: IRB00010471
Approval Number Federal Wide Assurance NIH, USA: FWA00018774

December 31, 2020

IRB Log Number: 20-772

Department: Nursing/Faculty of Management and Development Studies

Category of Approval: EXEMPT

Dear Ms. Abigail Ruth Asis,

I am pleased to inform you that your submission dated December 23, 2020 for the study titled '**Perceived Conflict and Professionalism among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia**' was reviewed and was approved according to ICH GCP guidelines. Please note that this approval is from the research ethics perspective only. You will still need to get permission from the head of department or unit in KFMC or an external institution to commence data collection.

We wish you well as you proceed with the study and request you to keep the IRB informed of the progress on a regular basis, using the IRB log number shown above.

Please be advised that IRB for administrative purposes requires that you submit a progress report on your research every 6 months. You are required to submit any manuscript resulting from this research for approval by IRB before submission to journals for publication.

As a researcher you are required to have current and valid certification on protection human research subjects that can be obtained by taking a short online course at the US NIH site or the Saudi NCBE site followed by a multiple choice test. Please submit your current and valid certificate for our records. Failure to submit this certificate shall a reason for suspension of your research project.

Sincerely yours,

Dr. Dania Al-Jaroudi

Chairperson, Second Health Cluster Institutional Review Board (IRB)

King Fahad Medical City

Tel: + 966 1 288 9999 Ext. 21100

E-mail: daljaroudi@kfmc.med.sa

Saudi Arabia - Riyadh
King Fahad Medical City
Faculty of Medicine
Phone: 0112889999

المملكة العربية السعودية - الرياض
مدينة الملك فهد الطبية
كلية الطب
لدور السابع
هاتف: ٠١١٢٨٨٩٩٩٩

APPENDIX C

UPOU ERB APPROVAL

UPOU IREC FORM 6(A): APPROVAL LETTER TO THE STUDY PROTOCOL

University of the Philippines Open University
INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Los Baños, Laguna 4031
Tel. Nos: (6349) 536 6001 to 6006 loc. 301, 420; 536 6014

24 February 2021

Asis, Abigail Ruth

Principal Investigator/ Researcher
c/o Faculty of Management and Development Studies
University of the Philippines Open University

Re: Decision of UPOU IREC for Study Code: UPOU MAN202106

Title of the Study: Perceived Conflict and Professionalism among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia

Dear **Ms. Asis:**

We wish to inform you that your study protocol has been reviewed and is hereby granted approval for implementation by the **UP Open University Institutional Research Ethics Committee (UPOU IREC)** but have to revise according to the comments made by the reviewers. Your study has been assigned study protocol code **UPOU MAN202106**, which should be used for all communication to the UPOU IREC Review panels (Ms. Maria Cecilia E. Punzalan and Dr. Josephine D. Agapito) related to this study. This ethical clearance is valid until 24 February 2022.

¹While the study is in progress, we request you to submit to us the following documents:

1. Progress report using the attached UPOU IREC Form 3(B): Continuing Review Application Form every Quarter of the year of the start of the Ethics Approval which includes the following: (*NOTE: In view of active ethical clearance, this report is mandatory even if the study has not started or is still awaiting release of funds.*)
 - a. Date covered by the report
 - b. Protocol summary and status report on the progress of the research
 - c. Number of participants accrued
 - d. Withdrawal or termination of participants
 - e. Complaints on the research since the last UPOU IREC review
 - f. Summary of relevant recent research literature, interim findings and amendments since the last UPOU IREC review
 - g. Any relevant multi-center research reports
 - h. Any relevant information especially about risks associated with the research

1

UPOU IREC MAN202106 24February 2021Asis

Page 1 of 2

University of the Philippines Open University
INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Los Baños, Laguna 4031

Tel. Nos: (6349) 536 6001 to 6006 loc. 301, 420; 536 6014

- i. A copy of the informed consent document
2. Any amendment/s in the protocol, especially those that may adversely affect the safety of the participants during the conduct of the research including changes in personnel, must be submitted or reported using the attached UPOU IREC Form 3(A): Study Protocol Amendment Submission Form.
3. Revisions in the informed consent form using the attached UPOU IREC Form 3(A): Study Protocol Amendment Submission Form.
4. Notice of early termination of the study and reasons for such using UPOU IREC Form 3(E): Early Study Termination Application Form.
5. Any event which may have ethical significance.
6. Any information which is needed by the UPOU IREC to do ongoing review
7. Notice of time of completion of the study using UPOU IREC Form 3(C): Final Report Form.
8. Application for renewal of ethical clearance 90 days before the expiration date of this approval through submission of UPOU IREC Form 3(B): Continuing Review Application Form, if the study will continue beyond expiration date of ethical clearance.

For more information including UPOU-IREC forms, you can ask the UPOU-IREC Project Staff at marian.tatlonghari@upou.edu.ph.

Thank you.

Very truly yours,

Dr. Ricardo F. Bagarinao
 Chair, UPOU IREC

Cc Dr. M Oruga, Marian Tatlonghari

APPENDIX D

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Informed Consent

University of the Philippines Open University

This informed consent form is for hospital King Fahad Medical City and who I am inviting to participate in my research entitled “Perceived Conflict and Professionalism among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia”

Name of Principle Investigator: Abigail Ruth Asis, RN

Name of Organization: University of the Philippines Open University

Name of Project: Thesis N300

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the study with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you choose to participate)

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction

I am Abigail Ruth Asis, taking Master’s Degree in Nursing. I am doing research on determining the significant relationship between perceived level of conflict and professionalism of nurses in a Tertiary hospital in Saudi Arabia. I am going to give you information and I would like to invite you to be part of my research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research. This consent form may contain words that you do not

understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask me.

Purpose of the research

This research aims to contribute to the knowledge specifically, assess the level of perceived conflict and professionalism and determine the relationship to one another, among nurses in King Fahad Medical City.

Type of Research Intervention

This research will involve your participation in answering a research questionnaire with 48 questions based on Perceived Conflict Scale and Valiga's Concept of Nursing Scale among nurses and it will take approximately 15 minutes to accomplish.

Participant Selection

You are being invited to take part of this research because you are a Nurse employed in King Fahad Medical City for more than 6 months and above as defined for this study who can contribute much to our understanding and knowledge about the level of perceived conflict and professionalism and to determine the relationship to one another, among the nurses in King Fahad Medical City.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. If you choose not to participate all the services you receive at this hospital will continue, nothing will change and there will be no negative consequences. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may stop participating at any time and you may decide not to

answer specific questions without any risk to self. Completion of the two Questionnaires used in this study denotes voluntary participation with no anticipated long-term physical effects and minimal (if any) long-term emotional or psychological effects from participating in the study. You may or may not have some degree of discomfort when relating experiences with conflict and professionalism in the workplace. However, participation in this study is voluntary and you have the right to decline anytime without punishment. I will maintain an open line of communication with you to answer tool-related queries. Additional information will be provided in this consent form which includes my email address.

Procedures

I am inviting you to take part in this research. If you accept to participate in this research study, the following will occur:

1. I will be distributing Self-administered questionnaires to all the hospitals and centers in King Fahad Medical City after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review board, Nursing Research Committee in the hospital and Ethical review board in the University of the Philippines.
2. Permission from the Director of Nursing or the authorized person is obtained prior to distribution of the questionnaires.
3. The questionnaires will be handed to you personally, or if not, these will be entrusted to the Head Nurse as per your duty schedule.
4. I will be directly contacting you to ensure acknowledgment of the questionnaires, secure informed consent, answer any related questions and for follow up purposes.

Duration

The Questionnaire will take 15 minutes. This will take place in a location you are most comfortable such as in the hospital during break time or in your home. You may ask questions as you wish.

Benefits

If you decide to participate, there are no direct benefits to you. No incentives are offered. However, the potential benefit to nurses is better understanding and knowledge gained by determining the significant relationship between perceived conflict and professionalism among nurses. Although there may be no direct benefit to you, the possible benefit of your participation is that you will be contributing to additional insights regarding conflict and professionalism which may result in the improvement of policies and practices at your hospital.

Confidentiality

The research being done may draw attention but we will not be sharing information about you to anyone outside of the research team. The questionnaires will have no participant identifiers (names, initials, or employee numbers, name of hospital). After accomplishing the questionnaire, the participant will directly place in a sealed envelope and it will be collected by the investigator to be secured in a locked cabinet. The investigator had no access to the respondents' name or addresses. The printed data and paper version will be stored and locked in a cabinet. Electronic data will be locked in a computer file with a password on my computer. The information that I collect from this research project will be kept private. Participant's identity will be maintained confidential and will remain secure even when results of the study will be presented to conference

or be published in journal. All Records will be destroyed 3 years after the completion of the research project.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so, and choosing to participate will not affect your work and there will be no penalty. You may stop participating in answering the questionnaire anytime.

Part II: Certificate of Consent

I have been invited to participate in research about Perceived Conflict and Professionalism among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia.

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: _____

Statement by the researcher/person taking consent

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands that the following will be done:

1. Participation in answering the questionnaire.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Signature of Researcher /person taking the consent: _____

Date: _____

Appendix E

QUESTIONNAIRE

Sociodemographic Background:

Please complete the following background information (Please check the appropriate box)

1. Are you employed in the hospital?
 - Yes (please continue with the questionnaire)
 - No (please do not continue with the questionnaire- Thank you for your time)

2. Age
 - Less than 30
 - 30-39 years' old
 - 40 years old and above

3. Marital Status
 - Single
 - Married

4. Gender
 - Male
 - Female

5. What is your educational level?
 - Diploma Degree
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's Degree
 - Ph.D.'s Degree

6. What is your job position?
 - Staff Nurse
 - Nurse Manager (Nursing Director, Nurse Manager, Unit Manager, Shift Manager)

7. Nationality _____

8. How long have you been working as a Nurse in the hospital?
 - above 6 months to 1 year
 - 2-4 years
 - 5-9 years
 - 10-14 years
 - 15 years and above

Perceived Conflict Scale

Instruction: Please encircle the one response that most accurately represents your feelings.

Perceived Conflict Scale	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
Interpersonal Conflict					
1. Another nurse often disagrees with each other about how to work on this unit should be handled.	SA	A	U	D	SD
2. My supervisor and I usually agree with what my job is, and the requirements I must fulfill.	SA	A	U	D	SD
3. Patients often demand that I do things that I just cannot do.	SA	A	U	D	SD
4. When I do something that satisfies one person or group, other people are frequently upset with what I have done.	SA	A	U	D	SD

Intrapersonal Conflict					
5. My obligations to my work frequently conflict with my obligations to my family, friends, or myself (outside the job).	SA	A	U	D	SD
6. I often cannot get equipment, supplies, or medications when I need them.	SA	A	U	D	SD
7. I often have too many things to do at one time.	SA	A	U	D	SD
8. I usually agree with the decisions my supervisor makes.	SA	A	U	D	SD
9. My patients often make requests or need care that I feel I should provide but cannot because I lack the time or energy.	SA	A	U	D	SD
Intragroup Conflict					
10. I frequently encounter problems when I transfer my patients to other units or departments.	SA	A	U	D	SD
11. I usually agree with the way other nurses think things should be done on this unit.	SA	A	U	D	SD
12. Many times, the things that support services are supposed to do are not adequately done, and I either must argue with another unit, or do someone else's job.	SA	A	U	D	SD
13. I am unable to provide adequate patient care because of the time that I spend dealing with hospital rules.	SA	A	U	D	SD
Intergroup Conflict					
14. The employees that I see who are from other areas of the hospital are often difficult to deal with.	SA	A	U	D	SD
15. The various departments that I deal with in the hospital are usually helpful and make it easy to do my job.	SA	A	U	D	SD
16. Support services (Respiratory therapy, anesthesia techs.) are readily available when I need them.	SA	A	U	D	SD

Valiga's Concept of Nursing Scale

Instruction: This questionnaire is a measure of the beliefs which you currently hold about Outlook on Nursing as a Profession, the Job Position of the Nurse, and the Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members. Read each of the statements below carefully. Then, for each statement, please indicate whether you strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), are undecided or do not know, disagree (D), or strongly disagree (SD) with the statement. Encircle the one response that best expresses your opinion, and please be confident in your response to each statement are marked. Please do not answer with what you expect the nursing profession's leaders would say. Rather than an intellectual response, concentrate on the way you feel, what you believe. There are no right or wrong answers, so please respond as freely as you can.

Valiga' s Concept of Nursing Scale	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
Outlook on Nursing as a Profession					
1. The nurse must assume responsibility for diagnosing and treating human responses to actual or potential illness.	SA	A	U	D	SD
2. Nursing must be concerned equally with the prevention of disease and the conservation of health.	SA	A	U	D	SD
3. Nursing is an expression of one's commitment to others.	SA	A	U	D	SD
4. There is a right and wrong way to do things and to approach nursing situations.	SA	A	U	D	SD
5. The uniqueness of nursing lies in response to what nurses do in society, rather than in specific tasks they perform	SA	A	U	D	SD
6. There should be only one nursing theory.	SA	A	U	D	SD
7. Nurses should be free to practice nursing as they define it within the scope of professional autonomy.	SA	A	U	D	SD
8. Nurses should update their knowledge through lifelong continuing education.	SA	A	U	D	SD
9. Nurses must control and direct their practice.	SA	A	U	D	SD
10. Nurses must be aware that the people who require their assistance are helpless and dependent and usually need to be told what to do.	SA	A	U	D	SD
Job Position of the Nurse					
11. The independent functions of nurses include supervising the care of the clients/patients, observing and recording, supervising non-professional personnel, and health teaching.	SA	A	U	D	SD
12. Nurses must be involved actively in an professional organization.	SA	A	U	D	SD
13. Nurses should be responsible for conducting nursing care conferences routinely.	SA	A	U	D	SD

14. Nurses must assume responsibility for reviewing and evaluating the care provided by nursing peers.	SA	A	U	D	SD
15. Nurses must not hesitate to assume the role of the leader of the healthcare team when nurses best meet the client's/patient's problems.	SA	A	U	D	SD
16. Evaluation of the work of their peers and other nursing personnel should be the responsibility of nurses.	SA	A	U	D	SD
17. Nurses must take deliberate action to attain independence in a nursing situation.	SA	A	U	D	SD
18. Nurses should assume 19. responsibility for the total nursing care of a caseload of clients/patients.	SA	A	U	D	SD
Relationship of the nurse to the client, doctors, and other health allied members.					
20. Nurses must be willing to enter with clients/patients those health-related situations which they cannot face alone.	SA	A	U	D	SD
21. Nursing is concerned with helping people maximize their health potential in their life situations.	SA	A	U	D	SD
22. Over action, directed by logical thought, toward meeting the client's patient's need for help constitutes the practice of clinical nursing.	SA	A	U	D	SD
23. Nurses should make written or verbal contracts with all appropriate persons to assure continuity of nursing care of clients/patients.	SA	A	U	D	SD
24. Nurses should be concerned primarily with giving physical care to clients/patients as directed by a doctor.	SA	A	U	D	SD
25. Nurses must follow the doctor's orders without a question.	SA	A	U	D	SD
26. Nurses have responsibility for discussing the proposed medical plan of care with the doctor so that it can be adjusted, if possible, to be more acceptable to the client/patient.	SA	A	U	D	SD

ABIGAIL RUTH G. PADUA

Registered nurse

CONTACT INFO

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ST.
Middle Quezon Hill,
Baguio City
2600

+639193107343
apasis@up.ed.ph

EDUCATION

SAINT LOUIS UNIVERSITY
Baguio City

BACHELORS OF SCIENCE
IN NURSING
2003

OBJECTIVE

To assess quality needs,
develop plans, and
implement coordinated
initiatives based on best
practice options.

LEADERSHIP

Acknowledged for
significant contributions to
quality, patient safety and
satisfaction in my current
position.

SKILLS AND ABILITIES

Experienced professional skilled in establishing and maintaining effective managerial practices to foster a high-performance work environment. Demonstrated expertise in creating collaborative environments and implementing strategies that drive team success.

Strong ability to lead and facilitate meetings effectively. Excellent communication and interpersonal skills, enabling productive participation in discussions. Demonstrated expertise in Utilization Management, Customer at Risk, Care Planning, Quality Improvement, and related areas.

EXPERIENCE

KING FAHAD MEDICAL CITY, RIYADH KSA

SEPTEMBER 16, 2009- UP TO PRESENT

Unit Manager-Quality Women's Specialized Hospital Nursing Administration

Participates in planning, developing, deployment, training, monitoring and evaluation of management systems, care processes and nursing practice.

KING FAHAD MEDICAL CITY, RIYADH KSA

MARCH 7, 2009- SEPTEMBER 15, 2017

Shift Manager- Quality WSH Nursing Administration

Assess quality needs, plans and implement coordinates initiatives based on best practice options. Participates in and/or coordinates the development, trial, distribution, in-service, review and recording/filing of nursing forms, policies and procedures and other key documents.

KING FAHAD MEDICAL CITY, RIYADH KSA

MAY 19, 2014- MARCH 6, 2016

Staff Nurse 1- Quality Women's Specialized Hospital Nursing Administration

Assists in development, implementation and evaluation of ongoing quality programs which assure quality nursing, and patient care programs, consistent with the KFMC mission and vision.

KING FAHAD MEDICAL CITY, RIYADH KSA

SEPTEMBER 9, 2009- MARCH 18, 2016

Staff Nurse 2- Nursery Women's Specialized Hospital Nursing Administration

Reviews clinical data from various sources including newborn assessment, feeding, laboratory investigations and vital signs and follows up if abnormal. Completes a history and physical examination of newborns. Performs or assist patient in performing newborn care.

EASTER COLLEGE INCORPORATED, BAGUIO CITY

JUNE 1, 2007- MARCH 31, 2009
Clinical Instructor- College of Nursing

Direct, manage, and evaluate learning in a clinical setting in line with current evidence/practice and underpinning curricula and syllabus as required. Observe, guides support, and supervises student nurses at ward/bedside level to assure competence and excellence in patient care

KING ABDUL AZIZ SPECIALIST HOSPITAL, TAIF, KSA

JULY 14, 2006- MAY 2007
Staff Nurse- Post Operative Ward (OB and Gyne)

Completes a history and physical examination. Ensures multidisciplinary patient problem list is commenced on admission and updated regularly. Documents all assessment findings in a timely, comprehensive and ongoing manner in accordance with relevant policies and procedures. Performs or assist patient in performing patient care.

PINES CITY DOCTORS' HOSPITAL, BAGUIO CITY

FEBRUARY 16, 2004- MAY 1, 2006
Staff Nurse 1- Nursery/NICU

TO PROVIDE ROUTINE NEWBORN CARE AND PROMPTLY REFER FOR ANY ABNORMAL FINDINGS. EXPERIENCE: - PROFICIENT IN PROVIDING COMPREHENSIVE NEWBORN CARE, ENSURING THE WELL-BEING AND HEALTH OF INFANTS. - SKILLED IN CONDUCTING ROUTINE ASSESSMENTS TO IDENTIFY ANY ABNORMALITIES OR POTENTIAL HEALTH CONCERNS.

PINES CITY DOCTORS' HOSPITAL, BAGUIO CITY

OCTOBER 2003- FEBRUARY 2004
Staff Nurse 1- General Wards (Medical-Surgical, Ob-Gyn, Pediatrics)

Maintain accurate record of patient care. Ensure the patient and family is provided with appropriate information/education to make informed decision relating to treatment, and care reflect their preference. Assess discharge planning. Care for patient pre- and post-operative ensuring pain and wound care are managed effectively and ensuring that pre-

operative preparation is completed in a timely manner to promote safety and comfort of the patient. Formulate plan of care based on individual patient and family need and ensure standard are met.
